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BURNOUT & STRESS REDUCTION IN PSYCHIATRIC NURSES THROUGH
MINDFULNESS-BASED STRESS REDUCTION INTERVENTIONS

A DOCTORAL PROJECT

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By

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ABSTRACT

Background: There are over twenty million healthcare workers at risk for mental health problems (MHP) in the U.S. due to demanding work environments. Research revealed that 93% of health workers endorse being stressed out, 82% feel mentally and physically drained, and 45% reported that they were not receiving adequate emotional support. Burnout (BO) and stress among PNs have been evaluated to be higher among other nursing specialties. Mindfulness-based stress reduction (MBSR) interventions efficiently reduce BO and stress among PNs. The evidence shows that MBSR interventions lowered the PNs work stress, while improving their emotional regulation and self-efficacy to relieve their negative emotions. The Kolcaba Comfort Theory guided this project. Purpose: Decrease the experience of BO and stress with the implementation of MBSR interventions in PNs. This project aimed to identify causes of BO and stress, assess changes in BO and stress levels before and after completing the implementation of MBSR interventions, and develop recommendations for management of BO and stress reduction for the PN. Methods: This QI project employed a pretest-posttest design. A convenience sample of 10 nurses at a psychiatric hospital participated in MBSR education sessions. The project survey collected participant's sociodemographic characteristics. Two validated tools; the Maslach Burnout Inventory-Human Services Survey (MBI-HSS) and Perceived Stress Scale-10 (PSS-10), measured BO and perceived stress levels. The data was collected before and after the completion of MBSR education sessions. Eligibility included participants to be 18 years old or older, English-speaking nursing staff, who provide direct psychiatric care to patients. Exclusion criteria included participants who reported experiencing exacerbating symptoms of mental illness. Daily MBSR usage was collected in a ballot box. QI macros® and Intellectus Statistics™ was used to analyze participant demographics and pre-test baseline data for BO and stress. Results: There was a statistically significant difference in EE, DP, PS levels between before and after implementation of MBSR implementation, respectively ($M=3.31$ vs $M=1.49$, $p<.001$; $M=1.60$ vs 0.74 , $p=.083$; $M=2.16$ vs $M=1.99$, $p=.301$). No statistically significant difference was observed in personal accomplishment ($M=4.06$ vs $M= 5.04$; $p=.059$). Overall, BO and stress was reduced and deep breathing MBSR intervention was used most readily. Implication for Practice: The future use of MBSR interventions to decrease BO and stress includes the PN and all nurses working in variable specialties. The everyday practice of mindfulness allows for MBSR interventions to be performed anytime, anywhere, or in response to a stressful situation. Recommendations for practice change include ongoing mental health service to mitigate BO and stress, APP reminders for MBSR daily use, and its inclusion in mental health wellness training for staff.

Keywords: Psychiatric nurse, burnout, stress, mindfulness strategies, stress interventions, emotional exhaustion, depersonalization, personal accomplishment, perceived stress

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Background

There are over twenty million healthcare workers at risk for mental health problems (MHP) in the United States (U.S.) due to demanding work environments (National Institute for Occupational Safety and Health [NIOSH], 2022). Demanding work environments entail the physical, emotional, and cognitive aspects of an individual's job (NIOSH, 2022). Healthcare professionals work in demanding environments which places them at risk of an injury due to fatigue and mental enervation caused by the experience of fluctuating emotions while working. The challenges experienced by healthcare workers are often inevitable; even prior to the current health crises occurring across the U.S. such as Coronavirus disease (COVID-19), Influenza, and Respiratory syncytial virus (Centers for Disease Control [CDC], 2022). Healthcare workers have had to continue to work despite these conditions. The challenges include long work hours, staff shortages, pressure from families and employers, and death, which are just a few of the many events that have plagued health workers over the years (CDC, 2022; Shah et al., 2020; Vidotti et al., 2018). Research found that 93% of health workers endorse being stressed out, 82% feel mentally and physically drained, and 45% reported that they were not receiving adequate emotional support (Al Sabei et al., 2022; Ghawadra et al., 2019; NIOSH, 2022; Yang et al., 2018; Zhang et al., 2020).

Healthcare workers consist of doctors, nurses, medical assistants, and many other professionals who serve in key support roles (CDC, 2022). Nursing is the largest profession in the U.S. making up 4.2 million Registered Nurses (RNs) nationwide (American Academy of Clinical Neuropsychology [AACN], 2022). Nursing care is vital and indispensable in the hospital setting as it helps to ensure the continuity of care delivered to patients is optimal (Vidotti et al., 2018). The role of the RN is intense; a nurse may be performing emergent life saving measures

to save a life at one moment, then the next minute will be implementing de-escalation tactics as a safety intervention for an aggressive patient. Psychological and physical workload are determinants of the RNs workload fatigue, which is what fuels a demanding work environment (Ahmadi et al., 2022). Consequently, research suggests that nursing has been identified as one of the most stressful professions to work in (Kaushik et al., 2021; Kim & Kweon, 2020; Maharaj et al., 2018). According to the U.S. Department of Labor National Center for O*Net Development (NCOD, 2022) nursing is ranked six out of 873 professions in which nurses experience work related mental distress. Mental distress can lead to anxiety, depression, post-traumatic stress disorder, substance abuse, job dissatisfaction, increased turnover, decreased quality of life, burnout, and stress (American Nurses Association [ANA], 2020; Da Rosa et al., 2021; Martinez-Ponce et al., 2023; National Alliance on Mental Illness [NAMI], 2023).

Burnout (BO) and stress will be the primary focus of this DNP Project. Burnout and stress among psychiatric nurses (PNs) has been evaluated to be higher among other nursing specialties (Kim & Kweon, 2020). According to Yang et al. (2018), the PN experiences higher stress levels, which has been associated with the negative perceptions that have been linked to patients with MHP (Yang et al., (2018). The PN may have a negative mental state, which has been attributed to the stress they work under and the types of patients they encounter (Yang et al., 2018). The chronic distress of an individual's job complicated by emotional exhaustion, negative emotions, and low professional morale are components of BO and stress (Dall'Ora et al., 2020; NIHCM, 2021). In particular, PNs who use themselves as a therapeutic healer have higher job stress compared to non-psychiatric nurses in other specialties (Cranage & Foster, 2022; Kim & Kweon, 2020). Psychiatric nurses provide direct care to the psychiatric patient who is a danger to themselves and others, or gravely disabled (Sim et al., 2020). The role of PNs

experience places them in high demand environments in working with patients with mental illness. Psychiatric nurses make up the second largest group of mental health professionals in the U.S. (American Psychiatric Nurses Association [APNA], 2023a). The scope and standard of practice for the PN articulates the engagement and compassion service toward those with MHP.

Engagement is a vital aspect of human service toward the psychiatric patient that impacts their recovery and influences quality of care (APNA, 2023b); Chambers et al, 2021; McAllister et al., 2021). The PN provides care to individuals who experience variable acute symptoms including but not limited to suicidality, mood irregularities, and psychotic symptoms (Wampole & Bressi, 2020). Consequently, these nurses must take action to restore one back to their baseline of functioning prior to their psychosis (Kim & Kweon, 2020). Therefore, PNs are challenged with even higher levels of mental distress since their work environment differs from non-psychiatric RN work environments (Kim & Kweon, 2020; Mukihata et al., 2022). Many of the interventions that can be used to help restore the patient back to their baseline are intensive to implement and can cause mental distress to the PN who is responsible for implementing interventions. These interventions include reporting to doctors, seclusion and restraint of the patient, or an emergent intramuscular injection of a psychiatric cocktail that consists of an antipsychotic, anxiolytic, and antihistamine to combat one's psychosis, anxiety, and side effects experienced (Sim et al., 2020; Zareifopoulos & Panayiotakopoulos, 2019).

Implementation of these interventions is difficult to provide to patients since they are often in a heightened agitated state of arousal (Tucker et al., 2020) which in turn fuels the consequences associated with working in a demanding work environment (Cranage & Foster, 2022). The consequences include cynicism, pessimistic attitudes, incivility toward other PNs, and lack of communication with others (Dall'Ora et al., 2020; Kelly et al., 2021). The PN who is

burned out may even leave their position all together (Penque, 2019; Poku et al., 2022; Schug et al., 2022). Their lack of motivation increases poor job performance which then insinuates poor quality of care to the psychiatric patient (Babapour et al., 2022).

Although stress may be found in any job, evidence indicates that work demands placed on nurses to care for sick and diseased patients have increased the effects of BO among working nurses (Fadzil et al., 2021; Ghawadra et al., 2019). Increased stress and depletion of working nurses' emotions may exacerbate BO which can lead to increased absenteeism, sick leave, and high turnover rates (Arredondo et al., 2017; Dall'Ora et al., 2020; Schug et al., 2022). Notably, BO is a significant predictor of musculoskeletal pain, headaches, cardiovascular disease, gastrointestinal problems, respiratory issues, and individuals are more likely to engage in substance abuse, and alcohol use (Chen et al., 2022; Jarrad et al., 2018; Salvagioni et al., 2017). Additionally, significant financial costs to the organization is noteworthy. According to Halter et al. (2017), a nurse quitting their job can cost an organization between \$11,000 to \$90,000 dollars and up to \$8.5 million in associated expenditures, such as open vacancies, trainings, and orientations.

There are effective interventions that can be utilized to alleviate mental distress among nurses since healthcare organizations, patients, and their families benefit the most from PNs who are not psychologically and physically fatigued (De Hert, 2020). The use of mindfulness-based stress reduction (MBSR) interventions were found to be efficient tools used to reduce BO and stress among PNs (Yang et al., 2018). The evidence shows that MBSR interventions lowered the PNs anxiety, depression, and work stress, while improving their emotional regulation and self-efficacy to relieve their negative emotions (Yang et al., 2018).

Mindfulness-based stress reduction techniques may include relaxation techniques, mindfulness-based cognitive therapy, acceptance of commitment therapy, loving-kindness, deep breathing, and compassion meditation to decrease burnout and stress in nurses (Yang et al., 2018). Research has proposed that MBSR interventions can be effective to relieve a health worker's mental unrest (Arredondo et al., 2017; Foley & Lanzillotta-Rangeley, 2021; Ghawadra et al., 2019; Green & Kinchen, 2021; Kabat-Zinn, 2003; Riet et al., 2018; Sulosaari et al., 2022; Tolouian et al., 2022).

Problem Statement

In a Southern California psychiatric inpatient hospital, it was noted that absenteeism rates, and the loss of PNs had increased in the past few years (College Hospital Enterprises [CHE], 2023; Renee Lewis [CEO], personal communication, February 10, 2023; Juan Diaz [Staffing Resource], personal communication, August 31, 2022). Currently, the hospital has a 24-hour on-call crisis team, medical and surgical psychiatric units, and both adult and young adult psychiatric units (CHE, 2023). The hospital averages 280 absentee days quarterly, which is approximately 1100 absentee days annually (Juan Diaz [Staffing Resource], personal communication, August 31, 2022) which has led to staff shortages on various inpatient units (IPU) units and on the Crisis Stabilization Unit (CSU) (Andrew Whynaught [CSU Director], personal communication, August 2022). Furthermore, MBSR interventions are not implemented in this hospital to combat the problem of BO and stress that nurses have experienced and expressed (Renee Lewis [CEO], personal communication, February 10, 2023). Implementation of such interventions is much needed in this project site to help PNs overcome their mental distress (Renee Lewis [CEO], personal communication, February 10, 2022; Andrew Whynaught [CSU Director], personal communication, August 2022).

Purpose Statement

The purpose of this project was to decrease the experience of BO and stress with the implementation of MBSR interventions in PNs who work in a CSU and IPU at a psychiatric inpatient hospital. The aims of this project were to (a) identify causes of BO and stress in PNs (b) assess changes in BO and stress levels before and after completing the implementation of MBSR interventions in PNs in a CSU and IPU at a psychiatric inpatient hospital and (c) develop recommendations for management of BO and stress reduction for the PN working at a psychiatric inpatient hospital.

Kolcaba Comfort Theory

A framework is used to guide clinical practice and aids in providing a structure in the approach of care a nurse might use when caring for patients (Bonnell & Smith, 2018; Grove & Gray, 2019). Middle range theories are sets of concepts that are less broad and seek specific results (Leandro et al., 2020). According to Kolcaba (2001) middle range theories arrange disciplinary thinking and influence practice. The Kolcaba comfort theory (KCT) was first published in 1994, and then was expanded to include institutional outcomes in 2001 (Kolcaba & DiMarco, 2005). It was revised to be more comprehensive in 2003 to include the development, testing, and application of the theory (Kolcaba & DiMarco, 2005). The KCT focuses on the relationship between the needs of a patient, nursing interventions that address those needs, comfort, and health outcomes (Kolcaba, 1994). Kolcaba believed that in stressful health care situations, unfulfilled needs for comfort are fulfilled by an intervening nurse (Kolcaba, 2001). To promote comfort, some interventions that are offered are consistent with relaxation, imagery, or therapeutic touch to elicit what Kolcaba describes as a positive whole person response (Kolcaba, 1994).

In the early development of the theory, Kolcaba performed a concept analysis that assessed literature from various fields of study, such as psychiatry, nursing, medicine, ergonomics, English, and psychology (Kolcaba & Kolcaba, 1991). This concept analysis fueled the idea of comfort being grouped into a two-dimensional grid (Kolcaba, 1992) that was derived from a review of historical and contemporary nursing (Kolcaba, 1994).

Dimension One

The first dimension of comfort consists of three concepts. The first concept is *Relief*, which is defined as an individual's needs met during a healthcare experience (Kolcaba & Kolcaba, 1991), such as the intervention of medication given to a patient by a nurse to alleviate their pain. The second concept is *Ease*, which is defined as an experience of calmness, and the third concept is *transcendence*, which is when an individual can conquer problems or pain that arise from stressful healthcare environments (Kolcaba, 2003).

Kolcaba then proceeded to put together a taxonomic structure of these concepts to signify their role in nursing practice. The horizontal cells on the taxonomic structure are interrelated with the vertical cells (Kolcaba, 2003). This structure guided the assessment, process, and evaluation of comfort (Kolcaba & Kolcaba, 1991). Kolcaba revealed that all three states of comfort entail a cohesive positive relationship to performance, which suggests a strengthening component to an individual in need of comfort (Kolcaba, 1994). Kolcaba believed that comfort was a holistic outcome that accounted for the person's whole-body response to a health care stimulus. Comfort is a desirable outcome for nursing care because it paves the way for an individual to engage in the physical, and/ or psychological performance of health during a health crisis (Kolcaba, 1994). Overall, the states of comfort are steadfast, overlapping, and interdependent (Kolcaba, 1994).

Dimension Two

The second dimension of comfort is the contexts in which comfort presents to an individual with unmet needs (Kolcaba, 1994). These contexts are derived from the idea of *holism*, which is referred to an individual's total state of being, and comfort is derived from any of the four contexts (Kolcaba, 1992). The first context is *physical*, which refers to sensations, homeostasis, and immune function in the body (Kolcaba, 2003). The second context is *psychospiritual*, which is defined as the internal consciousness of life, and one's understood relationship to a higher order or being (Kolcaba, 2003). The third context is *environmental*, which is the external background of an individual's environment, such as temperature, light, sound, smell, color, furniture, or landscape (Kolcaba, 2003). Lastly, *sociocultural*, is the interrelated family, and accompanying societal relationships an individual carries throughout their life (Kolcaba, 2003).

According to Kolcaba (1994), when the two dimensions of comfort are juxtaposed, the end result is a two-dimensional approach of comfort. Furthermore, when needs for relief, ease, and transcendence are met in the four contexts of a physical, psychospiritual, sociocultural, and environmental experience, a positive healthcare outcome manifests [(Kolcaba, 2003), See Table 1 of Appendix A)].

Conceptual Framework

In her efforts to build a conceptual framework, Kolcaba postulated that constructs build significance when they are coupled with other concepts (Kolcaba, 1994). Therefore, she used concepts developed in the theory of human press to structure her framework. In the model of human press, a stimulus situation is the initial reaction experienced by an individual who is going through a health crisis (Murray, 1938).

Human development is determined by the individual's impressions of whether they will succeed or fail while encountering the suggested stimulus situation (Kolcaba, 1994). The stimulus situation is equivalent to alpha and beta press (Kolcaba, 1994). Alpha press is the total of obstructing forces, positive (facilitating) forces, and interacting forces (Kolcaba, 1994). Beta press is the individual's perception of the summation of the forces in alpha press (Kolcaba, 1994). Obstructing forces are the total negative stimuli arising from a stimulus situation, such as stress (Kolcaba, 1994). Facilitating forces are interventions delivered by a nurse to meet the needs of an individual who is depleted by obstructing forces (Kolcaba, 1994).

Healthcare situations are translated by individuals in terms of the many interacting forces that influence perception (Kolcaba, 1994). Interacting forces are an individual's past experience, age, attitude, emotional being, and support system (Kolcaba, 1994). If the overall health outcome is positive, then Kolcaba believes that the expectation of other health situations will end positively, contributing to a unitary trend (Kolcaba, 1994). Unitary trend is defined as behavioral steps toward the achievement of a desired effect (Kolcaba, 1994). Positive behavioral steps lead to an orienting health theme, which facilitates growth toward positive health seeking behaviors that can enhance comfort (Kolcaba, 1994).

Internal behaviors occur at the cellular level, such as healing and immunity; external behaviors are related to self-care activities, such as exercise (Kolcaba, 1994). If an individual is incapable of conscious thought, the nurse can assess for levels of discomfort, and provide a greater level of comfort to enhance healing or a peaceful death (Kolcaba, 1994).

In the revised model, an initial holistic approach to a patient/family healthcare needs is assessed and met by comforting nursing interventions provided by the nurse. Intervening variables could be age; however, age is a variable that cannot be changed by a patient. If the

nursing intervention is effective, comfort is enhanced. There is a positive relationship between enhanced comfort and the participation in health seeking behaviors (Kolcaba, 2003). If patients and families participate in health seeking behaviors institutions have better outcomes in practice delivery, and the implementation of the best nursing policies [(Kolcaba, 2003), Appendix A].

The KCT Assumptions

The basic assumptions of the KCT are that human beings have holistic responses to challenging stimuli, and comfort was a desirable outcome significant to the discipline of nursing. In addition, human beings have sought to meet their basic human needs (Kolcaba, 1994). However, it is inevitable that nurses as therapeutic healers often ignore their own basic human needs in lieu of the comfort of their patients and families (Kolcaba et al., 2006a). Hence, why the application of the KCT was vital to this DNP project.

Integration of the Project into the KCT

This project sought KCT to enhance comfort in the PN who provided care to patients in a psychiatric hospital setting. There are direct relationships that exist between this project and the KCT. The variables related start with PNs health care needs of BO and stress acknowledged by their work organization. Comforting measures met the unmet needs of the PN through MBSR interventions. Some of the MBSR interventions were utilized through meditation and prayer, yoga, meditative walking exercises, body scanning via mindfulness, and deep breathing techniques (National Center for Complementary and Integrative Health [NCCIH], 2023; Nilsson 2022).

Intervening variables such as age; did not compromise the next stage of psychiatric wellness since the nurses had no control of those variables. Comfort was an immediate outcome manifested through comfort interventions (Kolcaba, 2003); for the PN, psychiatric wellness was

enhanced through the reduction of BO and stress in this DNP project. The PN engaged in health seeking behaviors, that continued to combat BO and stress when the stimulus situation occurred again.

The focus on best practices, and policies was highlighted in this project. The American Nurses Association (ANA) *Nursing Code of Ethics* was a source that the organization used that laid the foundation for the implementation of the best policy and practice for BO and stress reduction in PNs. According to the ANA (2015) *Nursing Code of Ethics*, Provision 9, the profession of nursing and its professional organizations articulate nursing values, maintain the integrity of the nursing profession, and collaborate principles of social justice into nursing and health policy.

According to Kolcaba et al. (2006b) the application of theory into practice required the KCT to be compatible with an organization's values and mission and is simple enough to guide practice. The recommendations for the reduction of BO and stress management through MBSR interventions for the PN governed the sustainability of practice as high-quality nursing care was delivered (Saleh et al., 2022). It is the mission of an organization to provide superior psychiatric healthcare service to meet the needs of patients, communities, and nursing staff (College Health Enterprises [CHE], 2023). With KCT the platform for professional nursing practice and the implementation of policy enhanced PNs job satisfaction, which was advantageous for the organization. If nurses are satisfied with their organization, this can lead to organizational benefits, patient care benefits, and benefits for the nurses. Some examples include higher patient satisfaction scores, higher nurse retention rates, cost reductions, decreased mortality rates, and less adverse patient events within that organization (Kolcaba, 2001; Kolcaba 2003; Perry et al., 2018).

When the comfort of nurses is enhanced, then commitment toward the organization is enhanced (Kolcaba et al., 2006a). This linear relationship created better healthcare outcomes for PNs and their patients. If all of these concepts were not in alignment then the PN would have struggled to find a better healthcare outcome, which could have affected the PNs health seeking behaviors, and their psychiatric wellness while working (Appendix B).

Use of Kolcaba's Comfort Theory in Research and Practice

The KCT had been tested and embraced in several patient populations (Kolcaba & Dimarco, 2005; Kolcaba & Wilson, 2002; Krinsky et al., 2014; Qian et al., 2020). This theory was used in women going through radiation therapy who were battling early-stage breast cancer (Kolcaba & Fox, 1999), individuals dealing with urinary frequency and incontinence (Dowd et al., 2000), and individuals near the end of life (Novak et al., 2001). Within these studies the concept of comfort paved the way for nurses to meet the unmet needs of these patients.

In a recent study, Vo (2020) assessed the mental impact of COVID-19 on frontline workers. The KCT was utilized to guide and serve as a protective barrier against burnout and stress while combatting COVID-19. Through safe social distancing activities, and self-care that enhanced comfort, mental BO and stress was reduced (Vo, 2020). Similarly, Wei et al. (2020) used the KCT to guide nurses on strategies to combat BO in pediatric critical care settings. Self-care strategies that promoted the mental health to reduce BO and stress in nurses included finding one's purpose at work, nurturing work relationships, and fostering a positive attitude while working in a challenging work environment (Wei et al., 2020). Other current studies utilized this theory to investigate the effects of comfort care on symptoms of patients with dyspepsia, discomfort in patients in intensive care units and discomfort in nurses working on those units, as well as comfort nursing for patient improvement on pressure ulcers, falls, quality

of life, and intracerebral hemorrhage (Berntzen et al., 2020; Wang et al., 2021; Xiong et al., 2019).

The KCT was a good fit for this DNP project because it employed a holistic nursing practice approach that promoted change and governed the best healthcare outcome for patients, families, and nurses. Additionally, the KCT concepts provided a strong foundation for the PN to be reinvigorated with a holistic approach to service the mentally distressed patient in a psychiatric crisis and inpatient hospital setting. Through KCT guidance PNs sought healthy behaviors through internal and external exploration which influenced the overall improvement of psychiatric wellbeing.

Review of Literature

This literature review focused on current research on BO and stress reduction in PN through MBSR interventions. Grove and Gray (2019) state that evidence-based guidelines derive from synthesizing the literature on a clinical problem; therefore, the sources obtained in this literature review have validated the implementation of MBSR interventions to reduce BO and stress for the PN in a psychiatric inpatient hospital.

The research approach aimed to identify scholarly published studies. The databases utilized included Cumulative Index to Nursing and Allied Health Literature (CINAHL), PubMed, PsychINFO, and Google Scholar. The search terms and other synonyms combined with Boolean operators were used in the search. The terms included "psychiatric nursing," OR "community mental health nursing," AND "burnout," OR "occupational stress," OR "compassion fatigue," OR "emotional fatigue," OR "vicarious trauma" OR "secondary trauma" AND systematic review OR meta-analysis OR randomized controlled trial. Expanding the source critique allowed for reference lists to be searched as well. Inclusion criteria consisted of peer-reviewed studies written in English within the last five years as well as studies that coincided with BO or stress reduction through MBSR interventions for the PN or general healthcare professional. Over 75 studies that targeted other health services populations, such as emergency medicine, oncology, or operating room nursing, were excluded. Articles that focused on preexisting mental health issues, such as anxiety, depression, and psychotic disorders were excluded as well. The search yielded 145 studies; 22 were included. The review of the literature included one systematic review (Bekelepi & Martin, 2022), one systematic review and meta-analysis (Lopez-Lopez et al., 2019), and one critical review (Green & Kinchen, 2021). Overall, there were twenty quantitative studies with various designs that included four cross-sectional

(Alabi et al., 2021; Hasan & Tumah, 2018; Kim & Kweon., 2020; Konstantinou et al., 2018), six quasi-experimental (Alenezi et al., 2019; Fadzil et al., 2021; Foster et al., 2018; Owens et al., 2020; Penque, 2019; Wampole & Bressi, 2020), seven randomized control trials (Ameli et al., 2020; Askey-Jones, 2018; Bernburg et al., 2019; Hilcove et al., 2021; Yang et al., 2018; Yildirim & Yildiz., 2022; Zarvijani et al., 2020), one descriptive correlational design study (El-Azzab et al., 2019), and one descriptive survey design study (Tununu & Martin, 2020).

Burnout and Stress Amongst Psychiatric Nurses

Psychiatric nurses are exposed to high-stress work demands as they provide psychiatric care to individuals experiencing mental distress (Bernburg et al., 2019; El-Azzab et al., 2019; Kim & Kweon, 2020; Konstantinou et al., 2018; Tununu & Martin., 2020; Yang et al., 2018; Zarvijani et al., 2020). High work stress can be triggered by distressed and volatile psychiatric patients, thus creating intense work challenges (Hasan & Tumah, 2018). Moreover, the emotional toll it plays on the role of PNs is significant according to its relationship with burnout (Alenezi et al., 2019; Kim & Kweon, 2020; Konstantinou et al., 2018; Penque, 2019).

Generally, healthcare providers are burned out and stressed while providing care to patients; however, the PN in particular, who uses themselves as a healing tool, has higher job stress in comparison to other nursing specialties (Kim & Kweon, 2020; Lopez-Lopez et al., 2019; Yang et al., 2018). In addition, the challenge of excessive demands creates a disadvantage within the PN because of the inadequacy to fulfill the demands while working in the psychiatric setting (Bekelepi & Martin, 2022; Hasan & Tumah., 2018; Wampole & Bressi, 2020).

Consequently, research suggests PNs are at increased risk of BO due to challenging mental health work environments (Alenezi et al., 2019; Kim & Kweon, 2020; Konstantinou et al., 2018;

Maslach & Leiter, 2016). Therefore, PNs must handle stress well and develop strong coping skills to stay healthy over time (Bernburg et al., 2019).

Despite the robust literature that recognizes demanding work tasks performed by nurses, minimal studies focus on supportive interventions that alleviate mental distress for nurses (Alenezi et al., 2019; Bernburg et al., 2019; Sarazine et al., 2021). As for the PN, there is a clear need for enterprising approaches that aim at BO and stress reduction given their challenging work environment (Askey-Jones, 2018; Foster et al., 2018; Owens et al., 2020; Wampole & Bressi, 2020).

Burnout

The term burnout was initially established by Freudenberger in 1974 when he witnessed a lack of motivation and unwillingness to work within a mental health clinic (Freudenberger, 1974). Needless to say, these workers were burned out. Burnout is a syndrome of mental exhaustion and negative emotions that health workers manifest while working (Maslach & Jackson, 1981). For many years, BO has been identified as a work peril for various people-oriented professions (Maslach & Leiter, 2016). Burnout is a psychological syndrome that has emerged as a chronic response to stressors in the occupational environment (Maslach & Leiter, 2016).

The most universally used definition of BO consists of 3 components: emotional exhaustion (EE), depersonalization (DP), and personal accomplishment ([PA] Maslach, 1986). Similarly, Konstantinou et al. (2018) defined BO as a psychological condition that leads to diminished physical and mental energy exacerbated by chronic unresolved work-induced stress and inefficient coping strategies. The widespread negative impact that BO has on the occupational setting and those workers who are chronically exposed to such hazards has led the

World Health Organization (WHO) to include the syndrome in its International Classification of Diseases ([ICD-11]). According to Wampole & Bressi (2020), BO within the PN results from the work stress generated in the psychiatric inpatient work setting. Moreover, a stressful work environment fuels BO (Alenezi et al., 2019; Konstantinou et al., 2018).

According to Maslach et al. (2001) the term BO has been used by different people to mean contrasting things, so a basis for the problems and solutions to BO has not always clearly been defined; nonetheless, this has led researchers to develop a multidimensional theory of BO to be used as a predominant theoretical framework in the field of BO.

Emotional exhaustion is the first dimension of BO and the most pertinent quality. When individuals describe it, they most often refer to the experience of exhaustion (Konstantinou et al., 2018; Maslach et al., 2001). Tununu and Martin (2020) described it as the depletion of emotional resources leading to the inability to give themselves to a patient psychologically. In a systemic review of the prevalence of BO with 868 PNs, 25% had high EE (Lopez-Lopez et al., 2019). Tununu and Martin (2020) found that psychiatric nursing assistants had a significantly higher level of EE. An increase in EE was found in 44.4% of PNs in a study on two Nigerian psychiatric hospitals, suggesting its association with a poor quality of life (Alabi et al., 2021; Owens et al., 2020). Moreover, a significant positive correlation was found between EE and stress (Green & Kinchen, 2021; Lopez-Lopez et al., 2019; Sarazine et al., 2021; Zarvijani et al., 2020). On the contrary, mild symptoms of EE were revealed in a pilot study of a social work-led mindfulness-based intervention that addressed BO and stress in the PN (Wampole & Bressi, 2020). Despite mild symptoms of EE, the nurses indicated that their work ignited frustration and other stress responses that included emotional distance from their patients (Konstantinou et al., 2018; Wampole & Bressi, 2020).

Overall, high levels of EE were detected in various studies of the literature, while EE was not found at all in a study on PNs working in the Western Cape of South Africa (Alabi et al., 2021; Alenezi et al., 2019; El-Azzab et al., 2019; Kim & Kweon, 2020; Konstantinou et al., 2018; Sarazine et al., 2021; Tununu & Martin, 2020).

The second dimension is DP, which is defined as an undesirable, pessimistic attitude, and negative emotion toward patients (Askey-Jones, 2018; Tununu et al., 2020). According to Konstantinou et al. (2018), DP is characterized by distancing oneself from patients, which is an immediate response to exhaustion. Konstantinou et al. (2018) found that 24.4% of the PN's evaluated for BO and potential predictors demonstrated high DP. These results are consistent with other studies (Alenezi et al., 2019; El-Azzab et al., 2019; Konstantinou et al., 2018; Wampole & Bressi, 2020). On the contrary, DP was found to be low in PNs working in Nigeria and the Western Cape of South Africa (Alabi et al., 2021; Tununu et al., 2020).

The third dimension, PA or lack thereof, is the propensity to see oneself negatively regarding one's work with patients (Tununu et al., 2020). Konstantinou et al. (2018) deemed it a consequence of EE and DP or an integration of the two. Researchers found the prevalence of low levels of PA across multiple studies (Alabi et al., 2021; Alenezi et al., 2019); El-Azzab et al., 2019; Konstantinou et al., 2018). On the other hand, PA was high among nurses in South Africa and the US, respectively (Tununu et al., 2020; Wampole & Bressi, 2020).

The three dimensions of burnout establish a framework for how the PN can approach BO interventions to reduce BO effects on one's mental health. MBSR interventions must be used appropriately in this DNP project to mitigate the adverse effects of BO and stress within the PN.

Stress

Stress is an innate human emotion and an integral part of daily interactions (Hasan & Tumah, 2018; Zarvijani et al., 2020). Nurses experience disproportionately elevated levels of stress in the workplace; however, the PN must work under an even higher level of stress juxtaposed to nurses in other specialties (El-Azzab et al., 2019; Fadzil et al., 2021; Hasan & Tumah, 2018; Hilcove et al., 2021; Kim & Kweon, 2020; Yang et al., 2018; Zarvijani et al., 2020). A recent survey conducted by Mental Health America, (2023 [MHA]) found that 93% of healthcare workers were stressed and worn out too thin. One of the largest groups of respondents in the survey was nurses, which accounted for 22% of the overall responses included in the survey.

Stress can be viewed as the mental and physical force that falls outside an individual's coping boundaries (Green & Kinchen, 2021; Hasan & Tumah, 2018). Perceived stress (PS) and its influence can be measured using different indicators (Hilcove et al., 2021). In addition, biomarkers can be utilized to assess levels of PS stress that may be found in the working nurse (Hilcove et al., 2021). Research suggests the driving forces behind the PN's declining mental state directly correlate with psychiatric nursing job duties (El-Azzab et al., 2019; Hasan & Tumah, 2018; Kim & Kweon., 2020; Yang et al., 2018). Thus, this formidable force threatens the overall well-being of the PN (Hasan & Tumah, 2018; Yang et al., 2018).

The Perceived Stress Scale (PSS) was utilized across multiple studies in the literature (Ameli et al., 2020; Bernburg et al., 2019; Fadzil et al., 2021; Green & Kinchen, 2021; Hilcove et al., 2021; Sarazine et al., 2021; Zarvijani et al., 2020). The PSS questionnaire contains seven scales with 30 items that measure PS on a four-point Likert scale (Bernburg et al., 2019). On the contrary, the Depression, Anxiety, and Stress Scale (DASS 21) was also used in multiple studies

in the literature (Fadzil et al., 2021; Foster et al., 2018). The values for stress range between (0 and 14). Research confirms the DASS 21 reliability in assessing mental health quality in nurses (Fadzil et al., 2021; Foster et al., 2018). Similarly, two additional tools were used to measure stress. The Job Stress Scale (JSS) was used to measure stress in 108 PNs in South Korea, and the Psychiatric Nurse Job Stress Scale (PNJSS) was used to measure stress in 120 PNs in Egypt (El-Azzab et al., 2019; Kim & Kweon, 2020).

The Psychiatric Nurse Job Stress Scale contains a 22-item questionnaire that focuses on psychiatric nursing ability, the attitude of patients, nursing, and communication (El-Azzab et al., 2019). Overall, a statistically significant reduction in scores for stress in the PN and the general nurse was confirmed through MBSR interventions and measured appropriately throughout multiple studies (Alenezi et al., 2019; Ameli et al., 2020; Bernburg et al., 2019; Fadzil et al., 2021; Foster et al., 2018; Green & Kinchen, 2021; Yang et al., 2018; Yildirim et al., 2022; Zarvijani et al., 2020).

Predictors of Burnout and Stress

Research has revealed a significant relationship between BO and stress in the PN who works in the psychiatric work environment. It is imperative to acknowledge profiles of individuals at risk of acquiring BO and stress to facilitate the appropriate MBSR intervention for the PN in this project (Alenezi et al., 2019; Lopez-Lopez et al., 2019).

In multiple studies, researchers identified predictors associated with BO and stress in working healthcare professionals (Kim & Kweon, 2020; Lopez-Lopez et al., 2019; Konstantinou et al., 2018; Tununu et al., 2020; Yang et al., 2018). In this respect, multiple studies have shown that work elements, such as job satisfaction, work experience, and shift schedules, are predictors of BO and stress risks (Alenezi et al., 2019; Lopez-Lopez et al., 2019; Tununu et al., 2020).

Additionally, sociodemographic factors, such as being older or being a single male and having no children, suggests that nurses are more prone to BO and stress (Alabi et al., 2021; El-Azzab et al., 2019; Hasan & Tumah, 2018; Konstantinou et al., 2018; Lopez-Lopez et al., 2019; Tununu & Martin, 2020; Yang et al., 2018).

Tununu and Martin (2020) found that PNs in the Western Cape of Africa found that low levels of BO and stress were related to a high number of female PNs (61.5%) over male PNs (38.5%) in the work setting. Additionally, PNs were found to be more prone to BO and stress based upon age, and whether the female PN were widowed, divorced, or separated (Hasan & Tumah, 2018; Konstantinou et al., 2018). Research has concluded that as age increases, EE, DP, and PA diminish over time (El-Azzab et al., 2019). The literature supports that older age and being of the male gender, may serve as predictors of having higher BO in relation to EE.

According to Lopez-Lopez et al. (2019), DP exacerbates negative affectivity, stress (10.7%), driving distance to work, age, seniority, role conflict, aggression, exhaustion, organizational commitment, and moral distress, which are all considered factors of burnout and stress (Alabi et al., 2021; Konstantinou et al., 2018; Lopez-Lopez et al., 2019; Tununu & Martin, 2020; Yang et al., 2018). Correlations were found between aggression while working and quitting the psychiatric nursing profession altogether is correlated to BO and stress (Lopez-Lopez et al., 2019; Kim & Kweon, 2020; Sarazine et al., 2021). Overall, the literature concluded that predictors of BO and stress was role confusion, role ambiguity, satisfaction with pay, presence of severe family problems, fast turnover of staff, physical and mental unrest, and diminished quality of patient care (Alenezi et al., 2019; Lopez-Lopez et al., 2019; Kim & Kweon, 2020; Konstantinou et al., 2018; Sarazine et al., 2021). Although these factors were

made apparent in the literature, research suggests that overall, the PN does acquire a sense of job satisfaction over time, which is also a predictor of BO (Alabi et al., 2021).

A study on 120 PNs working in two psychiatric hospitals in Egypt found that more than half of the PNs had moderate levels of BO (51.7%) and stress (52.5%), and two-thirds (76.7%) of them had diminished self-efficacy (El-Azzab et al., 2019). Two studies performed in Saudi Arabia on PNs in two psychiatric hospitals revealed that the nurses had high levels of BO (Alabi et al., 2021; Alenezi et al., 2019; Hasan & Tumah, 2018). An inconsistent result with these findings reveal PNs admitted to not suffering from BO and stress at all in a psychiatric hospital in the Western Cape of Africa (Tununu & Martin., 2020). Nonetheless, the overall levels of BO according to the dimensions of EE, DP, and PA were moderate to high across four quantitative studies (Alabi et al., 2021; Alenezi et al., 2019; El-Azzab et al., 2019; Hasan & Tumah, 2018). As a result, research revealed that the moderate to high levels of BO and stress found in the PN has a linear relationship to poor quality of life, role conflict, and poor funding, which were considered additional predictors of BO (Alabi et al., 2021; Alenezi et al., 2019; Lopez-Lopez et al., 2019; Kim & Kweon, 2020; Konstantinou et al., 2018; Sarazine et al., 2021).

In a systematic review and meta-analysis on the prevalence of BO in PNs and related factors, 41.9% of BO and stress is linked to role conflict, family issues, and moral distress (Bekelepi & Martin, 2022; Konstantinou et al., 2018). Other factors that have been linked to the risk associated with BO and stress are years of work experience, complex patients assigned to the PN, low compensation, coworker conflicts, poor relationships with physicians, stress in the PN's private life, and job insecurity (Alabi et al., 2021; Penque, 2019; Tununu & Martin, 2020).

Nurses struggle with health problems more than the average healthcare provider (Owens et al., 2020). A growing body of literature suggests that compassion fatigue (CF) and its linkage

to BO and secondary traumatic stress (STS) have been identified as primary contributing factors to BO for nurses (Owens et al., 2020). Compassion fatigue is a stress response involving the tripartite of oneself; spiritual, mental, and physical well-being that becomes exhausted from the enduring sacrifice and exposure to challenging situations (Owens et al., 2020). Secondary traumatic stress is the empathetic connection with those who have experienced significant trauma (Owens et al., 2020). Secondary traumatic stress and the costs of providing care to an individual who experiences it have influenced BO elements (Owens et al., 2020).

Consequences of Burnout and Stress

Burnout and stress significantly impact nursing practice and the standard of care the psychiatric patient receives (Tununu & Martin, 2020). The quality of care for patients with mental health issues is directly linked to the quality of life lived by mental health staff charged with delivering the proposed psychiatric care (Alabi et al., 2021; Askey-Jones, 2018). Psychiatric nurses overwhelmed by BO are less likely to provide the highest quality of patient care (Alabi et al., 2021; Askey-Jones, 2018). According to Alenezi et al. (2019), BO is linked to a withdrawal from psychiatric care units, which means the ability to provide MBSR interventions is lost; less time in a psychiatric care unit has a linear relationship to poor quality of care delivered to the psychiatric patient. Poor quality of care leads to poor patient outcomes (Alenezi et al., 2019; Sarazine et al., 2021). The detrimental impacts of stress on PNs are increasingly evident (Foster et al., 2018). What has driven the interest in MBSR interventions within the psychiatric work environment is the elevated costs of sick absenteeism related to stress among PNs (Alabi et al., 2021; Askey-Jones, 2018). Konstantinou et al. (2018) revealed that BO could lead to alcohol impairment, diminished immunological systems, muscle pain, and depressive disorders. Similarly, El-Azzab et al. (2019) revealed that BO leads to petulant behaviors, tiredness, fatigue,

head pain, poor gut health, anger, insomnia, exhaustion, dyspnea, and excessive weight gain or loss (Alabi et al., 2021; El-Azzab et al., 2019). Burnout can also lead to excessive absenteeism, job dissatisfaction, high turnover rates, and poor work efficiency (Alabi et al., 2021; Alenezi et al., 2019; Askey-Jones, 2018; Kim & Kweon, 2020; Konstantinou et al., 2018; Lopez-Lopez et al., 2019; Sarazine et al., 2021).

The consequences of BO and stress in nursing have been studied worldwide; however, increasing research is needed to address BO and stress in the PN. Psychiatric nurses working in intense psychiatric units are challenged by providing quality patient care due to burnout's harmful risks and consequences (Bekelepi & Martin, 2022). Suitable MBSR interventions can aid the PN in overcoming the obstacles associated with BO and stress. MBSR interventions must be implemented to mitigate these effects in this DNP project (Foster et al., 2018).

Psychiatric Nurses

According to the APNA (2023a), psychiatric-mental health nurses make up the second largest class of behavioral health professionals in the U.S. There are 4.238 PNs per 100,000 total in the U.S. (WHO, 2019). Psychiatric nursing is a specialty within the field of nursing that furnishes holistic care to those who suffer from mental distress (APA, 2023). Psychiatric nurses form relationships by communicating with patients to build safety and comfort within the psychiatric setting (APA, 2023). The responsibilities of the PN derive from the nursing process, and therapeutic relationship developed through the provision of comfort care given to the psychiatric patient (Kumar et al., 2020).

According to the APNA (2023a), PNs are well educated mental health professionals that practice according to a rigorous licensing and credentialing domain that requires time to study the psychiatric practice of nursing accordingly. The expertise of the PN is necessary to assess,

diagnose, intervene, and evaluate the psychiatric patient efficiently. The PN must possess compassion, empathy, and willfulness in order to perform their job effectively. These qualities are essential to the PN duties of care for the psychiatric patient.

The overarching stress theme is significant to the psychiatric patient-and-nurse relationship (El-Azzab et al., 2019; Yang et al., 2018). According Wampole & Bressi (2020), PNs noted valuable elements of interpersonal relationships with patients. However, it was suggested that relationship-based responsiveness to the psychiatric patient experiences is a critical component of a social worker's skill set, not specifically a psychiatric nurses. Nonetheless, research suggests that because the PN is exposed to stress on the frontline, they develop genuine relationships with psychiatric patients as they care for them, which makes the approach much different from a social work-led approach (Tununu & Martin, 2020). This runs parallel to the fact that nurses work 365 days a year on the frontline of contact with patients (Konstantinou et al., 2018). Through constant contact with patients, Kim and Kweon (2020) suggested a significant relationship exists between job stress and communication lines with patients or staff in a psychiatric workplace setting. This could be in the context of witnessing the psychiatric patient's emotional distress, interpersonal conflict with coworkers, or daily personal challenges within the PN (Foster et al., 2018). Thus, when a patient is a danger to themselves or others or is gravely disabled, the PN prevents them from harm to themselves or others, which signifies a different stressful interaction of care. Moreover, the psychiatric patient may present with unpredictability and unstable behavior, which fuels the challenge and demands of nursing care distributed to the patient, consequently leading to BO (Tununu & Martin., 2020). Burnout is a continual stress reaction (Konstantinou et al., 2018).

Mindfulness-based Stress Reduction Interventions

Research suggests that MBSR interventions can be helpful in reducing BO and stress (Alenezi et al., 2019; Fadzil et al., 2021; Green & Kinchen, 2021; Wampole & Bressi, 2020; Yang et al., 2018). The MBSR program, developed by Kabat-Zinn in the 1970s, is the gold standard meditation modality for mindfulness and serves as a framework for many modern mindfulness programs (Askey-Jones, 2018; Green & Kinchen, 2021). Mindfulness involves directing one's thoughts and emotions to the present, here and now moment, yet in a non-judgmental manner (Bernburg et al., 2019; Fadzil et al., 2021; Green & Kinchen, 2021; Wampole & Bressi, 2020). By focusing one's thoughts on the present moment, ruminative practices are reduced, lowering stress levels (Wampole & Bressi, 2020).

According to Yang et al. (2018), psychiatric nurses' mental state remains in a state of tension. If an individual works under prolonged stress, the body's function declines, leading to various mental health problems. Therefore, the significance of the work of PNs is directly correlated with more tremendous work stress. Yang et al. (2018) suggest that more tremendous work stress reduces the PN's mental health stability. Therefore, strengthening the mental health of PNs is of the highest priority. Finding effective interventions for BO and stress experienced by PNs is needed to enhance stress-beating capacity and improve an individual's mental state, self-efficacy, and job performance (El-Azzab et al., 2019).

Mindfulness therapy containing meditation, physical awareness, yoga, mindful breathing, and stretching are MBSR interventions that are effective strategies for reducing BO and stress in the PN (Fadzil et al., 2021; Hilcove et al., 2021; Wampole & Bressi, 2020; Yang et al., 2018). According to the National Center for Complementary and Integrative Health (NCCIH, 2023), the meditation concept involves focus on the mind and body through awareness on the present moment. Physical awareness involves stretching muscles that are overworked and strengthening

muscles that are weak. This can be accomplished through yoga practices, which emphasize body postures of the spine and extremities, as well as breathing deeply into the lungs and out of the mouth (NCCIH, 2023).

Doctor Jon Kabat-Zinn developed a program that utilized meditative practices to treat chronic pain and then named his program MBSR (Green & Kinchen, 2021; Sarazine et al., 2021). The program was structured around eight weeks for 2.5-hour sessions each week, 45 minutes per day (Sarazine et al., 2021). Similarly, Alenezi et al. (2019) implemented a BO prevention workshop on 296 nurses and found that BO was reduced on all three subscales of the MBI. Due to the rigorous demands of the nursing settings identified in the literature, MBSR training was time sensitive, which allowed for the nurses to attend training without disrupting patient care duties (Askey-Jones, 2018; Green & Kinchen, 2021; Owens et al., 2020; Sarazine et al., 2021). The results indicated a positive outcome suggesting BO implementation interventions can be used to change stress coping styles within PNs. A study conducted on 100 PNs in three hospitals in China over a four-month time frame utilized MBSR interventions that included relaxation preparation via a relaxed posture while listening to relaxing music, mindfulness breathing, and mindfulness meditation (Alenezi et al., 2019; Yang et al., 2018; Yildirim et al., 2022). The results revealed that the intervention group demonstrated a statistically significant difference ($P < 0.001$) which signified that MBSR interventions were conducive to reducing work stress and enhancing the mental health of the PN (Alenezi et al., 2019; Yang et al., 2018). Intervention groups across multiple studies ranged from 32 to 296 nurses (Alenezi et al., 2019; Owens et al., 2020). In addition, many studies used mindfulness training sessions to educate the nurses on performing the MBSR techniques (Alenezi et al., 2019; Bernburg et al., 2019; Foster et al., 2018; Yang et al., 2018; Zarvijani et al., 2020). The educational training aimed to assist PNs

in developing their nursing abilities and identify what hinders them from achieving job satisfaction (Bekelepi & Martin, 2022).

An essential challenge to MBSR implementation is the time needed for practice, training, and MBSR intervention engagement (Ameli et al., 2020; Sarazine et al., 2021). Overall, MBSR interventions were delivered over a range of various timeframes, for example, 3-minute sessions over 4 weeks, 6-hour sessions per day for two days, and 1.5-2 hours sessions for seven days (Alenezi et al., 2019; Wampole & Bressi, 2020; Zarvijani et al., 2020). Despite MBSR interventions showing positive results, identifying the major obstacle of time during the implementation of MBSR for nurses was revealed (Fadzil et al., 2021). The time required to attend MBSR training practices seemed to interfere with the implementation; therefore, researchers sought to implement brief MBSR interventions to reduce stress in nurses from various specialties (Fadzil et al., 2021). The results revealed an improvement in the average PS score, thus suggesting that a brief MBSR intervention can yield positive mental health enhancements for the PN who works in the inpatient psychiatric setting (Alenezi et al., 2019; Ameli et al., 2020; Bernburg et al., 2019; Fadzil et al., 2021; Wampole & Bressi, 2020; Yang et al., 2018).

A 3-minute-deep breathing framework was suggested in the research to perform when automatic pilot thinking occurs during a stressful work shift (Owens et al., 2020). Within a 3-minute timeframe, the PN can envision themselves watching their thoughts as if they are on a large TV screen, then let go of this unique view in the second minute by focusing on breathing thru the nose and out of the mouth (Owens et al., 2020; Yildiz, 2022). Finally, in the third minute, the PN can focus their attention on their body by acknowledging bodily sensations that come forth (Owens et al., 2020). On the contrary, researchers suggested that nurses can perform

MBSR interventions learned during training in the privacy of their own homes (Yang et al., 2018).

Various effective interventions have been utilized to alleviate stress for nurses working in the psychiatric environment (Bekelepi & Martin, 2022; Foster et al., 2018). Relaxing music, debriefing support groups, muscle relaxation via muscle stretching and deep breathing exercises are well-suited MBSR interventions to reduce BO and stress for the PN in this DNP project (Alenezi et al., 2019; Owens et al., 2020). Two studies evaluated focus groups where participants shared their experiences, evaluated specific mental health constructs, received peer support, developed coping strategies, and practiced relaxation techniques (Alenezi et al., 2019; Foster et al., 2018; Hilcove et al., 2021; Yang et al., 2018). However, no study proposed managerial interventions such as lessening the workloads of PN. Foster et al. (2018) identified this factor as a research gap that needs to be addressed.

The studies included in this literature review have strengths and limitations discussed by researchers. The absence of follow-up measuring tools that assess long-term effects of MBSR interventions and minimal male participation was found to be a limitation in multiple studies across the literature (Askey-Jones, 2018; Bernburg et al., 2019; Fadzil et al., 2021; Owens et al., 2020; Sarazine et al., 2021; Yildirim & Yildiz, 2022; Zarvijani et al., 2020). Thus, male participants may have been burned out or stressed during the course of the studies intervention and as a result chose not to participate in the study. Also, small sample sizes were seen in multiple studies across the literature (Ameli et al., 2020; Askey-Jones et al., 2018; Bernburg et al., 2019; Sarazine et al., 2021; Wampole & Bressi, 2020; Yang et al., 2018; Yildirim & Yildiz, 2022; Zarvijani et al., 2020). Research suggests that small sample sizes limit the result's external validity (Bernburg et al., 2019). External validity focuses on whether studies can be generalized

in sample populations other than the PN population, which is significant to future MBSR interventions used to mitigate BO and stress. Additionally, more extensive study groups are recommended to assess feasibility and effectiveness in different nursing work settings (Bernburg et al., 2019; Konstantinou et al., 2018). Another limitation was that cross-sectional design studies in the research did not allow for causal relationships between different variables to be formulated. Thus, variables were only identified at one point in time (Alabi et al., 2021; Kim & Kweon., 2020; Konstantinou et al., 2018). Furthermore, longitudinal designs are recommended to further understand BO and stress in the PN in future studies (Kim & Kweon, 2020).

Randomized control trials were utilized in multiple studies across the literature, which is a strength within the literature review (Ameli et al., 2020; Askey-Jones, 2018; Bekelepi & Martin, 2022; Bernburg et al., 2019; Green & Kinchen, 2021; Hilcove et al., 2021; Lopez-Lopez et al., 2019; Yang et al., 2018; Yildirim & Yildiz, 2022; Zarvijani et al., 2020). Randomized controlled trials are noted to be the strongest methodology for measuring the efficacy of an intervention due to the elements of the design that reduce the potential for bias or error (Grove & Gray, 2019).

Overall, the levels of evidence for the studies included in this literature review range from RCT, which is considered level one evidence; quasi-experimental, which is level two evidence and cross-sectional design studies, which is level three evidence (Grove & Gray, 2019). Multiple studies were used from different countries other than the U.S. which paves the way for diversity and inclusion in clinical trials (National Institute on Minority Health and Health Disparities [NIMHD], 2023). Psychiatric nurses in different countries may experience BO and stress differently; therefore, it is essential that research includes diversity within clinical trials to support BO and stress reduction through MBSR interventions (NIMHHD, 2023). Inclusivity in

research can only benefit the advancement of scientific discovery in future studies. Strengths of the studies included the acknowledgment of MBSR research being added to the nursing profession to mitigate BO and stress in PN, as well as lower attrition rates and intervention fidelity, which ensures consistency and reliability of outcomes related to MBSR interventions (Ameli et al., 2020; Alenezi et al., 2019; Askey-Jones et al., 2018; Bekelepi & Martin, 2022; Bernburg et al., 2019; Green & Kinchen, 2021; Grove & Gray, 2019; Fadzil et al., 2021; Foster et al., 2018; Penque, 2019; Sarazine et al., 2021; Yang et al., 2018; Yildirim et al., 2022).

Methods and Evaluation

The purpose of this DNP project was to decrease the experience of BO and stress in PN who work in a Crisis Stabilization Unit (CSU) and Inpatient unit (IPU) at a psychiatric inpatient hospital in Orange County. This project aimed to identify causes of BO and stress in PNs, assess changes in BO and stress levels before and after implementing MBSR education, and provide recommendations on BO and stress management. The approach utilized sought to achieve BO and stress reduction in the PN and magnify the quantitative paradigm suggested in the literature for an evidence-tested approach that yields a positive outcome (Bonnel & Smith, 2018).

Project Design

This project utilized a pretest-posttest, single-group interventional design to reduce BO and stress through MBSR interventions. The benefits of the pretest-posttest design allowed researchers to implement an intervention, thus allowing for data collection through straightforward statistical tests (Alessandri et al., 2017). To supplement the collection of data, a run chart, which is an illustration of graphical data plotted in order, allowed for an easy interpretation of the results (Provost & Murray., 2011). In addition, a control chart was used to illustrate how the data collected changed over a specific time frame (Provost & Murray., 2011). Internal validity is the scope of the effects identified in the project reflecting a true sense of reality rather than the result of extraneous variables (Grove & Gray, 2019). A limitation of a pretest-posttest, single-group design is the threat to internal validity presenting as history bias, which are events unrelated to the reduction of BO and stress through MBSR interventions (Handley et al., 2018). For example, PN may recall negative or positive emotional responses to BO or stress that may have occurred before MBSR implementation. The pretest-posttest design

in this project sought to obtain an accurate reflection of cause and effect by the most efficient means as causality was examined. (Grove & Gray, 2019).

Setting

The project setting was a private community-based teaching hospital located in the city of Costa Mesa in Orange County. The hospital specializes in full-spectrum psychiatric care, medical-surgical care that includes drug and alcohol detoxification, and partial hospitalization programs, all of which treat adult and adolescent patients. In addition, the CSU and IPUs provide psychiatric treatment for adults aged 18 and older. The most common psychiatric conditions seen in the CSU and IPUs were depression, anxiety, psychotic disorders that include schizophrenia, schizoaffective disorder, bipolar disorder, personality disorders that include borderline presentations, mood disorders, post-traumatic stress disorder, alcoholism, and substance use disorders.

There are four IPUs of varying acuities. The north unit has the highest psychiatric acuity that contains male patients. The west unit is for high-acuity female patients. The east unit is for moderate acuity male and female patients. The south unit is for moderate acuity male and female patients awaiting long-term Institutions for Mental Disease placement. The CSU, also known as a Mental Health Urgent Care Facility, provides 23-hour crisis stabilization for patients who can walk in or are dropped off by law enforcement or sent by emergency departments via ambulance to the hospital. There are 16 recliner chairs available for patients of mild acuity to be treated in the CSU; however, moderate to severe acuity patients can present in the CSU depending upon inpatient bed availability.

Sample/Participants

This project utilized convenience sampling to recruit participants from the CSU and IPUs at the project site. The PN, licensed vocational nurses (LVN), and psychiatric nursing assistants (PNA) who work in the CSU and IPUs are male and female. In the CSU, the ratio is one PN to four psychiatric patients, and in the IPUs, the ratio is one PN to six psychiatric patients. Inclusion criteria consisted of English-speaking nursing staff, PNs, LVNs, and PNAs aged 18 years or older, and those who provide direct psychiatric care to patients in the CSU and IPU. Exclusion criteria included participants who reported experiencing exacerbating symptoms of psychiatric health diagnoses. Participants may have been vulnerable to coercive pressures that could impose increased stress, therefore, causing an exacerbation of their psychiatric diagnosis (Humphreys et al., 2015). Approximately 30 psychiatric nursing staff were projected to participate in the project.

Ethical Considerations

The Institutional Review Board (IRB) was obtained from the project site and California State University Fullerton (Appendix C). Permission to use the project site was obtained from the Interim Chief Executive Officer, (Appendix C). Voluntary participation was honored, and participants were asked to sign a consent form after reading it carefully, and all questions were answered by the project author (Appendix D). The project assumed minimal risk of harm to the participants due to the use of confidential data collection surveys. Participants had the choice to not answer any of the survey questions. Identifying information was not collected. Pre-and post-surveys were administered and numbered based on the order they were received. All information was kept confidential and securely locked on the PI password-protected laptop in a locked safe in a locked office. Any participant who wished to withdraw from the project did so freely and did

not bear any penalty or consequence. Participants were reassured that the results of this project were reported collectively.

Measures

Procedure

Participants were recruited immediately upon IRB approval. Flyers were posted and distributed in the CSU and IPU breakrooms (Appendix E). Emails were securely sent to work emails of all psychiatric nursing staff at the hospital. The project investigator (PI) also attended unit meetings and met with managers, supervisors, and charge nurses of each respective unit to discuss the project. The PI encouraged participants to ask questions and address any concerns they might have had during the project implementation. Once participation was confirmed, consent forms were distributed for careful review and signature. The consent form provided information on the purpose and aims of the project as well as outlined what would be asked of each participant if they chose to participate in the study. Benefits, risks, confidentiality, costs, and participant rights were covered on the consent form. Lastly, any questions participants may have had, as well as the contact information of the PI and IRB staff, was included on the consent form.

After signing the consent form, the participants were asked to complete the pre-survey of the project, which took 15 minutes or less to complete. Mindfulness-based stress reduction interventions were taught by the PI, (Appendix F). Plans to teach MBSR interventions on the various units were set for Monday through Sunday for one week, depending upon staff schedules and availability. The MBSR interventions included mindfulness music therapy, body relaxation via muscle stretching, deep breathing, and meditation (Alenezi et al., 2019; Yang et al., 2018). Plans were made to conduct training via multiple sessions; with inclusion of all PNs on the unit.

Each session was set to be approximately 30 minutes or less. Participants were asked to perform the interventions at home and while working as appropriate. Performance of MBSR interventions occurred three times daily or more. For example, if participants were triggered by an event on the unit, such as a patient who was trying to hurt themselves or others, the PN could partake in MBSR interventions on their break, at the nurse's station, or whenever they deem themselves fit enough to practice MBSR interventions. After the completion of MBSR interventions at work and at home, the post-survey was redistributed to the participants after the end of the third month of the study.

Data Collection

Data collection occurred via self-report electronic surveys before implementing MBSR interventions and at the end of implementation. The project electronic survey included the MBI-HSS, and the PSS-10, Appendix G. The electronic pre-survey also included the following demographics: age, gender, education level, marital status, years of work experience, and employment status (Appendix H). A ballot box with a simple questionnaire that assessed if the participants performed MBSR interventions was used to collect data daily while at work (Appendix I). The PI checked in with the participants weekly over the project timeframe.

Maslach Burnout Inventory-Human Services Survey

The Maslach Burnout Inventory-Human Services Survey (MBI-HSS) is recognized as healthcare professionals' chief guiding measure of burnout (Maslach & Jackson, 1981). The Maslach Burnout Inventory (MBI) scale was initially developed by Christina Maslach in 1981. Various versions were then developed, focusing on specialty groups (Ma'mari et al., 2020). For this project, the MBI-HSS is the most widely used scale designed for nurses working in challenging environments. The MBI-HSS has three scales: EE has nine items, DP has five items,

PA has eight items. Twenty-two items account for the frequency of emotions and attitudes toward patients and the work environment on a five-point Likert scale ranging from 1 to 5 (never to every day).

A study on mindfulness workshop effects on nurses' BO and stress found that the MBI-HSS had overall high internal reliability and test-retest reliability for the three subscales (Sarazine et al., 2021). Reliability testing determined the measurement error in the MBI-HSS used in this project. Moreover, stability, equivalence, and internal consistency, which are pertinent aspects of reliability, were deemed fit in the study on mindfulness workshop effects on nurse BO and stress (Grove & Gray, 2019). Stability reliability focuses on the reproducibility of scores with repeated measures of the same attribute with an instrument over time (Grove & Gray, 2019). The test-retest reliability is determined by MBI-HSS stability which was found to be high in the study as well (Grove & Gray, 2019).

Furthermore, the results of the study proved that mindfulness interventions decreased BO and stress and enhanced mindfulness skills in nurses (Sarazine et al., 2021). Permission to use the MBI-HSS was granted; therefore, the use of the MBI-HSS commenced. The scoring key was lined up with the MBI-HSS survey document. The sum of the survey responses on EE was divided by the number of answered EE items. The average EE score was recorded. This scoring procedure was used for the DP and PA surveys as well.

Perceived Stress Scale-10

The PSS-10 is a 10-item questionnaire developed by Cohen et al. (1983) to assess stress in adolescent and adult populations. The perception of life according to how unpredictable, uncontrollable, and how overloading it can be was evaluated on the scale. The questions included feelings and cognition on stress experienced over the previous month of time. It took

approximately 10 minutes or less to fill out the survey. Participants are asked how often stress makes them feel at work on a five-point scale. The total score ranges from 0 to 40.

The overall PSS-10 score was calculated by reverse coding the positive items in the questionnaire and adding the scores for all of the items (She et al., 2021). Reverse scoring was beneficial because it negated undesirable responses that reflected acquiescence (Carlson et al., 2011). For example, a participant might have been asked a question on stress in the context of psychiatric work, and the expectation would be to then select responses according to high-stress levels pertaining to psychiatric nursing environments. Therefore, the scoring followed the reverse-coding format; 4 = 0, 3 = 1, 2 = 2, 1 = 3, 0 = 4 to avoid unnecessary coercion (Cohen et al., 1983). The PSS-10 was not used as a diagnostic instrument, and there was no score cut-off (Cohen et al., 1983).

The PSS-10 score was resulted by adding the items across the scale. Higher scores equated to higher levels of PS. A study on the psychometric components of the PSS-10 found that it demonstrated significant internal consistency reliability with $\alpha = .78$ and substantial validity with stress levels experienced during an average week; $r = .39, p < .001$ (Baik et al., 2017). A correlation coefficient r value indicated the significance of a relationship between two variables; in the study, stress, anxiety, and depression indicated a moderate relationship (Grove & Gray, 2019). A p-value that was less than 0.05 was considered statistically significant (Grove & Gray, 2019). The Cronbach alpha coefficient was used to measure internal reliability, which was found to be a strong coefficient in the study on psychometric components of the PSS-10 (Baik et al., 2017; Grove & Gray, 2019). The Permission to use the PSS-10 was granted.

Interventions

In the first stage of the training, relaxation commenced. The psychiatric staff were instructed to form a comfortable, relaxed posture, preparing the mind for meditation (Yang et al., 2018). They were asked to remove their shoes. Relaxing music was played to aid them in this process. The PI used oral prompts to lead them into a deeper relaxed state. Simultaneously, they were instructed to stretch their upper and lower extremities, neck, and back muscles.

In the second stage, mindfulness deep breathing via inhalation through the nose and exhalation through the mouth pushed the participant's body and mind to be aware of its limitations. This was done when the participant experienced rumination of negative thoughts while performing psychiatric care. The participants were instructed to practice deep breathing exercises every day for 10 minutes at home or during their work shifts. They then could choose the best time and place to perform MBSR interventions. Each week reminders were sent out to practice active mindfulness stretching, deep breathing, music therapy, and meditation. A written protocol was distributed to aid the participants with MBSR intervention practice (Appendix D).

The physical feelings of a tight or relaxed chest wall and compromised or uninterrupted airflow in the lungs through the mouth and nose prepared the staff for the third stage. Mindfulness meditation allowed the psychiatric staff to think about their thoughts, emotions, and attitude in the present time. The PI then invited the participants to leave aside their issues or concerns about their workplace, home, future, or self-judgments and focus on the present moment (Yildirim et al., 2022). Participants experiencing negative constructs were taught to release the negative emotion through acceptance and exchange the negative thought for a positive one. After completing the MBSR education, the PI contacted the participants via text message to check in with them and address any questions or concerns they might have had as

they performed the MBSR interventions. Data collection occurred over two months. The participants were encouraged to perform mindfulness interventions three times per day or in response to work environment triggers that presented. After the study, the MBI-HSS and PSS-10 was redistributed.

Project Timeline

Pre-test survey, implementation of MBSR interventions, and post-test survey were fulfilled from August 2023 through December 2023 (See Figure 3 of Appendix B).

Data Analysis

QI Macros® is a statistical software program that created charts and graphs for statistical process control, and Intellectus Statistics is additional software that conducted statistical analyses of reported data that allowed for simple communication of results obtained in this study. QI Macros® and Intellectus Statistics™ was used to analyze participant demographics and pre-test baseline data for BO and stress. Univariate analytics determined the mean (range), frequencies, and percentage of participant demographic characteristics, such as age, gender, marital status, education, employment status, and years of experience. Descriptive statistics analysis included averages, standard deviations, percentages, and frequency, which were used to assess BO and stress levels reported by the psychiatric nursing staff. A graph graphical illustration of how changes occurred over time was illustrated on a control chart (Provost & Murray, 2011). In this project, control charts plotted data points acquired daily from the participants who self-reported when they performed MBSR interventions in the work environment and at home. Paired sample t-Tests was used to assess any changes in BO and stress levels among the psychiatric nursing staff after the completion of the intervention. Burnout and stress pre- and post-surveys was used

to compare the average values of data collected. Evaluation and measurement of outcomes is displayed in Table 2 of Appendix J.

Results

The purpose of this DNP project was to decrease the experience of BO and stress in the PN who works in a CSU and IPU at a psychiatric hospital. The project aimed to assess changes in burnout and stress levels after completing MBSR interventions, identify causes of BO and stress in PNs, and provide recommendations on BO and stress management in the PN working in a psychiatric hospital. After completing the pre-survey, PNs received MBSR education in person at the project site on their breaks to avoid psychiatric patient care interruptions. After the MBSR education sessions, the PNs were asked to self-report MBSR interventions on a simple questionnaire that assessed whether the interventions were used at work or home. The simple questionnaire forms were placed inside a ballot box in their break rooms.

Sociodemographic Characteristics

Descriptive statistics, percentages, and frequencies were utilized to analyze participant demographic characteristics. Fourteen participants consented to participate in the pre-implementation survey. It should be noted that 4 participants did not wish to continue with the doctoral project and were removed from the analysis. Ten participants (N=10) completed the post-implementation survey. Most sample participants were female: 7 (70%) females and 3 (30%) males. Four participants (40%) were in the age range of 36-42, three (30%) were 29-35, two (20%) were 22-28, and one (10%) was 43-50. Of the 10 participants, 5 (50%) were married or in a domestic partnership, 4 (40%) were single, and 1 (10%) was divorced. Five (45.45%) nurses had five or more years of experience, 3 (27.27%) had 2-3 years of experience, (See Table 3 of Appendix K). All 10 participants participated in MBSR education and completed the pre- and post-survey.

Levels of Burnout: Emotional Exhaustion

Six participants (n=6) had high EE, with a frequency score of 27 or over. Three participants (n=3) had moderate EE, with a score between 17-26, and one (n=1) had low EE, with a score between 0 to 16. A statistically significant difference was observed between before MBSR implementation (M=3.31, SD=1.01) and after implementation (M=1.49, SD=0.82; $p<.001$), indicating there was overall improvement in EE in response to the use of MBSR interventions (See Table 4 of Appendix L). Sub-scale analysis of average participant EE before and after implementation is displayed in Figure 3 of Appendix L. The statement relating to feeling emotionally drained (M = 4.3, $p = .002$) was rated the highest among the participants, and the statement related to the stress of working with patients directly (M = 1.5, $p = .173$) was rated the lowest.

Depersonalization

Six participants (n=6) had high DP, with a frequency score of 13 or over. One participant (n=1) had moderate DP, with a score between 7-12, and three participants (n=3), had low DP, with a score between 0 to 6. A statistically significant difference was observed between before MBSR implementation (M=1.60, SD=1.10) and after implementation (M=0.74, SD=0.92; $p=.083$), indicating there was overall improvement in DP in response to the use of MBSR interventions, indicating there was overall improvement in DP in response to use of MBSR interventions (See Table 5 of Appendix L). Sub-scale analysis of average participant DP before and after implementation is displayed in Figure 4 of Appendix L. A sub-scale analysis of the statement related to the worry of the job making an individual feel emotionally hardened was rated highest (M = 2.5, $p=.043$) among the participants pre-intervention, and the statement

related to treating individuals as if they were impersonal objects was rated lowest ($M = 0.8, p = 3.99$) pre-intervention.

Personal Accomplishment

Six participants ($n=6$) had high PA, with a frequency score of 39 or over. One participant ($n=1$) had moderate PA, with a score between 32-38, and three participants ($n=3$) had low PA, with a score between 0 to 31. No statistically significant difference was observed between before MBSR implementation ($M=4.06, SD=1.38$) and after implementation ($M=5.04, SD=0.20; p=.059$), indicating there was no overall improvement in PA in response to the use of MBSR interventions (See Table 6 of Appendix L). Sub-scale analysis of average participant PA before and after implementation is displayed in Figure 5 of Appendix L. Two statements related to understanding how patients feel and the positive influence on patients through the PN work was rated highest amongst the participants ($M = 4.8, p=.068; M = 4.8, p=.394$) pre-intervention. The statement about feeling energetic while working was rated the lowest ($M = 2.9, p=.057$) pre-intervention.

Levels of Perceived Stress

For the PSS-10-Scale, there was a difference between before ($M = 2.16, SD = 0.20$) and after ($M = 1.99, SD = 0.37; t = 1.10, p=.301$) implementation of MBSR interventions (See Table 7 of Appendix L). Two participants ($n=2$) had high PS, scoring 27-40. Seven participants ($n=7$) had moderate PS, with a score between 14-26, and one ($n=1$) had low PS, with a score between 0 to 13. Questions 4, 5, 7, and 8 were reverse-coded. Question 4 asks, ‘In the last month, how often have you felt confident about your ability to handle your problems?’ Question 5 asks, ‘In the last month, how often have you felt that things were going your way?’ Question 7 asks, ‘In the last month, how often have you been able to control irritations in your life?’ and Question 8 asks, ‘In

the last month, how often have you felt that you were on top of things?’ A subscale analysis of the statement ‘In the last month, how often have you felt nervous or stressed’ was rated the highest ($M = 3.1, p=.001$) pre-intervention is displayed in Figure 6 of Appendix L. The statement, ‘In the last month, how often have you felt that things were going your way?’ was rated the lowest ($M = 1.5, p=.002$) pre-intervention.

Causes of Burnout and Stress

Analysis of burnout data via the MBI-HSS tool revealed causes of burnout in the PN to be related to the negative emotions of feeling drained (70%), fatigued (60%), frustrated (50%), and callous towards the psychiatric work environment and its patients (40%). Analysis of stress data via the PSS-10 tool revealed the causes of stress in the PN to be related to negative emotions of being upset over unexpected events (30%), inability to control things that occur in life (30%), lack of confidence to handle personal problems (20%), as well as the inability to cope and control irritations in life (20%).

MBSR Interventions Used

Four MBSR interventions were used as interventions for burnout and stress reduction in the project: deep breathing, muscle stretching, music therapy, and meditation. A summary statistics table for interval and ratio variables of MBSR interventions is displayed in Table 8 of Appendix L. Participants could utilize any of the four interventions they wanted while working and at home for 10 minutes. A bar graph display shown in Figure 7 of Appendix M demonstrates the cumulative total of MBSR interventions used. Data was collected daily and plotted on c-Charts, illustrating MBSR interventions used over the project timeframe. Special cause variations were noted in the C chart for deep breathing (See Figure 8 of Appendix M) and music therapy (Figure 9 of Appendix M) as indicated by a trend. Baseline data of the MBSR

interventions was collected over two weeks. MBSR interventions were increased after the start of MBSR education sessions, as shown in the aforementioned figures.

Deep Breathing, Muscle Stretching, Music Therapy, Meditation

The aggregated data results for MBSR intervention deep breathing was most readily used. Deep breathing use data revealed improvements in BO and stress ($M=12.00$, $SD = 44.96$, $SE_M = 5.90$, $Min = 1.00$, $Max = 348.00$, $Skewness = 7.38$, $Kurtosis = 52.67$). Improvement in burnout and stress was supported by the deep breathing c-chart showing special cause variation indication of a trend during October 2023. The aggregated data results for MBSR intervention muscle stretching were also used most readily by participants, as shown in Figure 10 of Appendix M. Muscle stretching use data revealed improvements in BO and stress ($M=7.55$, $SD = 28.38$, $SE_M = 3.73$, $Min = 0.00$, $Max = 219.00$, $Skewness = 7.32$, $Kurtosis = 52.03$). Improvement in burnout and stress was supported by the muscle stretching c-chart showing special cause variation indication of a trend during October 2023. The aggregated data results for MBSR intervention music therapy were used by participants, as shown in Figure 8. Music therapy data revealed ($M=7.07$, $SD = 26.55$, $SE_M = 3.49$, $Min = 0.00$, $Max = 205.00$, $Skewness = 7.33$, $Kurtosis = 52.15$), (Table 8, Appendix H). The aggregated data results for MBSR intervention meditation were used least often by participants, as shown in Figure 11 of Appendix M. Meditation data revealed ($M= 5.59$, $SD = 21.00$, $SE_M = 2.76$, $Min = 0.00$, $Max = 162.00$, $Skewness = 7.30$, $Kurtosis = 51.90$), (Table 8).

Discussion

Participant demographics included gender, age, education, employment, experience, and marital status. There was no significant difference in participant demographic characteristics pre- and post-survey. Most participants were bachelor's prepared, full-timed, married female nurses aged 36-42 with five or more years of experience. In multiple studies, researchers identified work experience as a predictor of burnout and stress (Alenezi et al., 2019; Lopez-Lopez et al., 2019; Tununu & Martin, 2020). Additionally, sociodemographic factors, such as being older or being a single male and having no children, suggested that nurses were more prone to burnout and stress in the psychiatric setting (Alabi et al., 2021; El-Azzab et al., 2019; Hasan & Tumah, 2018; Konstantinou et al., 2018; Lopez-Lopez et al., 2019; Tununu & Martin, 2020; Yang et al., 2018).

Most participants in this project were married females aged 36-42 with five or more years of work experience, which is inconsistent with findings in a study that suggested that married nurses experience a range of responsibilities that enable them to cope with stress triggers (Hasan & Tumah, 2018). Additionally, nurses with more experience can cope with higher stress levels by creating coping mechanisms based on personal experiences (Hasan & Tumah, 2018). While most PNs in this project had higher levels of EE and stress, this finding may reflect the multibranch nature of BO and stress in the psychiatric setting between the crisis and inpatient settings, as well as the varying measures associated with internal distress when working in challenging psychiatric environments. Research also suggested several other factors that were associated with burnout and stress in the PN, such as nurse shortages, interpersonal conflicts, new healthcare technologies, budget cuts, environmental surroundings, situational factors, and

exposure to tasks outside of psychiatric nursing responsibilities (Alabi et al., 2021; Alenezi et al., 2019; El-Azzab et al., 2019; Hasan & Tumah, 2018).

Burnout & Stress

This QI project offered insights into burnout and stress among psychiatric nurses who play a pivotal role in the delivery of care for psychiatric patients who have severe mental illnesses. Overall, the level of burnout and stress was reduced among all participants who utilized daily MBSR interventions in this project. Research has shown that mindfulness interventions were effective in decreasing burnout and stress (Arredondo et al., 2017; Foley & Lanzillotta-Rangeley, 2021; Ghawadra et al., 2019; Green & Kinchen, 2021; Kabat-Zinn, 2003; Riet et al., 2018; Sarazine et al., 2021; Sulosaari et al., 2022; Tolouian et al., 2022; Yang et al., 2018). Evidence shows that MBSR interventions lower stress by improving emotional regulation, self-confidence, and self-assurance (Yang et al., 2018). For example, neuroimaging studies support the positive effects of MBSR interventions on brain behaviors and cognitive channels on self-relational behaviors (Weder, 2022). Although mindfulness does not alleviate all issues that life may present, research suggests that it will allow for the opportunity to see problems that may arise in life with more precision (Sarazine et al., 2021), which speaks to the influence of MBSR intervention used to reduce burnout and stress levels.

Emotional exhaustion was considered moderate to high amongst the 10 participants pre-implementation versus post-implementation. A study revealed high levels of EE in PNs in Saudia Arabia and Greece, which is consistent with the findings in this project (Alenezi et al., 2019; Konstantinou et al., 2018). Inconsistencies with these results were revealed in the low EE levels in PNs working in a psychiatric hospital in the Western Cape of South Africa (Tununu & Martin, 2020). It was suggested that environmental surroundings and nursing rank played a part in the

result of those psychiatric nurses providing care in the Western Cape of South Africa. Tununu and Martin (2020) suggested that low levels of EE equate to higher levels of nursing practice. Advanced practice registered nurses and psychiatric nurses comprised most of the participants in that study. Most participants in this study are bachelor's prepared PNs, and many had moderate to high levels of EE. Nursing shortages may have affected the EE levels of PNs in this project.

Three participants had high levels of DP, one had moderate DP, and six had low DP. This finding is consistent with the results of a study of PNs working in the Western Cape of South Africa (Tununu & Martin, 2020). Most of the participants in that study had low levels of DP, which meant they were not burned out based upon DP criteria. Environmental and demographic factors were suggestive causes of the results in that study on PN in the Western Cape of South Africa. Additionally, six participants had high levels of PA, one had moderate levels of PA, and three had low levels of PA in this project. Although participants in this study met EE criteria for burnout, and had low levels of DP, they still felt high levels of PA, which speaks to the personal character of the participants and other demographic variables that were not measured in this study. Different levels of an individual's self-confidence in fulfilling tasks determine the choice of different character components, the degree of effort, the time of resilience, and the attitude orientation when completing a task (Yang et al., 2018).

On the contrary, researchers found low levels of PA prevalence across multiple studies (Alabi et al., 2021; Alenezi et al., 2019); El-Azzab et al., 2019; Konstantinou et al., 2018). One important reason for the different results is the countries where the studies were conducted, demographic characteristics, different measured variables such as depression and anxiety, and environmental factors. Overall, in this project, most participants were moderately burned out, experienced low levels of DP, and felt a high degree of PAON. The PNs at the project site may

be experiencing moderate levels of burnout because of age since most participants were between 36 and 42 years old, which is not advanced. Research suggests that BO decreases as the PN ages (El-Azzab et al., 2019). Additionally, most PNs were bachelor's prepared registered nurses, which is consistent with a study that suggested that higher education levels equate to high levels of burnout (Kobayashi et al., 2020).

This project indicated statistically significant decreased perceptions of stress post-MBSR implementation. Seven participants had moderate PS, two had low, and one had high PS. This stress level is comparable to a study of nurses in Malaysia and the US, which reported that most nurses and healthcare professionals had reported moderate to high levels of PS (Ameli et al., 2020; Fazil et al., 2021). Depression and anxiety are two variables that were measured along with stress in Malaysian nurses; anxiety, burnout, mindfulness components, and self-care were additional variables measured in healthcare professionals in the US, which may have amplified their stress levels while working in intensive environments. The results in this study differ from other studies based on participant characteristics, the exclusion of other mental health variables, such as depression, anxiety, compassion fatigue, resilience, and the location of this study being in the US.

The results provided cognizance of the effectiveness of MBSR interventions in reducing burnout and stress for healthcare workers, specifically psychiatric nurses. Tips for creating space for relaxation, breathing exercises, stress reduction management, and muscle stretching can benefit the PN working in any healthcare setting (Alenezi et al., 2019). There were robust research findings that supported MBSR interventions to mitigate burnout and stress in the working healthcare professional (Alenezi et al., 2019; Fadzil et al., 2021; Green & Kinchen, 2021; Owens et al., 2020; Wampole & Bressi, 2020; Yang et al., 2018). Nonetheless, this project

successfully applied KCT as a structure to reduce the unmet need of burnout and stress through the engagement of MBSR interventions: deep breathing, muscle stretching, music therapy, and meditation. The basic assumptions of the KCT are that humans have holistic responses to challenging stimuli and that comfort is a desirable outcome significant to nursing. Therefore, human beings seek to meet their basic human needs (Kolcaba, 1994). Comfort towards oneself as a PN can employ a positive approach to psychiatric nursing care, which ultimately influences the psychiatric patient care outcome. Comfort measures successfully met the unmet needs of the PN through MBSR interventions in this DNP project.

Mindfulness-Based Stress Reduction Interventions

The MBSR interventions successfully reduced stress levels and BO among this project's participants. Similarly, studies of mindfulness interventions reduced burnout and stress in healthcare workers in psychiatric settings (Fadzil et al., 2021; Hilcove et al., 2021; Sarazine et al., 2021; Wampole & Bressi, 2020; Yang et al., 2018). The revelation suggests that individuals working in an intensive work environment can benefit from efficacious MBSR interventions. Deep breathing was often used, followed by muscle stretching, music therapy, and meditation. Deep breathing was the most preferred technique in this project based on the ease of engaging an individual's nervous system through oxygen. Research confirms deep breathing directly influences brain structures regulating emotion, mood, and arousal (Balban et al., 2023). Once an individual inhales and exhales, the nervous system commands the entry of calmness and tranquility through chest expansion and relaxation. Essentially, this allows an individual's mind and body to be aware of its limitations, reducing burnout and stress.

Consequently, during this time, there were cases of COVID-19 identified in the hospital, which may have affected PN-to-patient ratios, burnout, and stress levels. Research suggests that

intense workloads and high levels of burnout and stress caused by the COVID-19 pandemic have exhausted the US nursing labor force and propose an emergent need for solutions to alleviate burnout and stress amongst nurses (Martin et al., 2023; Shah et al., 2021). Research suggests that MBSR deep breathing and music therapy reduce stress and fatigue in nurses under intense work stress (Owens et al., 2020; Yildirim & Yildiz, 2022).

As PNs provide care to psychiatric patients who are a danger to themselves and others or are gravely disabled, the potential for burnout and stress is inevitable. Yang et al. (2018) suggested that more intensive work stress reduces the PN's mental health stability. Therefore, strengthening the mental health of PNs is crucial to providing quality healthcare. Mindfulness-based stress reduction interventions for burnout and stress experienced by PNs are needed to enhance stress-beating capacity and improve an individual's mental state, self-efficacy, and job performance (El-Azzab et al., 2019).

Implications for Practice

The implications for practice revealed from this DNP project are significant. The future use of MBSR interventions to decrease burnout and stress includes the psychiatric nurse and all nurses working in variable specialties. Research confirms the robust awareness of burnout and stress in psychiatric nurses and many healthcare professionals in different specialty roles. Once an individual has practiced mindfulness interventions and learned to be mindful, it can be used at anytime, anywhere, regardless of any circumstance, to reduce burnout and stress (Green & Kinchen, 2021). With the ever-increasing psychological emotion of working in an intensive environment, MBSR interventions would be beneficial to reduce symptoms of burnout and stress. By reducing an individual's responsiveness to burnout and stress, mindful nurses may feel more relaxed and less susceptible to negative emotions (Green & Kinchen, 2021).

Reducing burnout and stress symptoms through MBSR interventions speaks to resources needed to support the emotional well-being of nurses working in an intensive work dynamic (Wampole & Bressi, 2020). Ongoing educational programs are suggested to instill and cater to developing optimistic attitudes toward psychiatric nursing environments (El-Azzab et al., 2019). The PN is considered a pivotal component of their environment for prime healing through optimizing their self-care practices, transmitting a calm and relaxed state to patients, and facilitating an optimal peaceful environment for healing (Hilcove et al., 2021). Future studies may benefit from a larger sample population integrating a control group. The psychiatric nurse should receive ongoing mental health service that caters to factors of burnout and stress as well as MBSR interventions. Additionally, the PN will improve their propensity to perform self-care habits that reflect KCT. The use of an APP to guide mindfulness techniques and set daily reminders to perform MBSR interventions is noteworthy. It is highly recommended that MBSR interventions be included in employee self-care wellness training.

Furthermore, the engagement of individual and institutional collaboration in reducing burnout and stress through MBSR interventions may propel favorable effects on individual health, patient outcomes, and organizational success (Ameli et al., 2020). Resources are urgently needed for education and nursing workforce development that addresses compassion fatigue, burnout, and stress in the PN (Marshman et al., 2021). The endurance that employs the provision necessary to provide consistent quality care to individuals who have severe mental illness takes responsibility and willfulness to provide quality health service. The results of this DNP project call for a deeper discussion of PNs', managers', and administrators' recruitment, training, and self-care needs of psychiatric nurses so that high-quality care is consistently delivered. Many areas for future studies should include a variety of MBSR interventions. The project time frame

was short; therefore, the longer-term effects of MBSR interventions with similar measured variables should be analyzed and compared.

Strengths and Limitations

The systematic approach created through QI Macros and Intellectus, supported by the well-planned implementation of MBSR education was a strength of this DNP project. The assurance of sustainable quality improvement efforts performed allowed for intricate data analysis to produce statistically significant results. As a result, a robust methodology approach can yield positive results for PNs experiencing BO and stress while working in an intensive psychiatric environment. Limitations were encountered during MBSR implementation. Psychiatric nurse participation was minimal which led to a small sample size recruited. Research suggests that small sample sizes limit the result's external validity (Bernburg et al., 2019). External validity focuses on whether studies can be generalized in sample populations other than the PN population, which is significant to future MBSR interventions to mitigate burnout and stress. Additionally, research suggests individuals exhibit behaviors that limit the expression of positive emotions in regard to the work environment (Fukuzaki & Iwata, 2023). The PNs in this project may have promoted a negative association between burnout and stress levels when working in an intensive psychiatric work environment.

Nonetheless, there was a significant change in burnout and stress levels after MBSR education. The data collected speaks to the clinical significance as evidenced by reduced burnout and stress levels in the PN. Lastly, the priority of MBSR education was halted by a burst of COVID-19-positive cases during the project's implementation. It is unconfirmed how much this may have impacted participation recruitment.

Conclusions

The use of MBSR interventions, such as deep breathing, muscle stretching, music therapy, and meditation, reduced the levels of burnout and stress in the PN who works in a psychiatric hospital. Implementing MBSR interventions to reduce burnout and stress applies to psychiatric IP hospitals and many other nursing specialties, such as emergency rooms, labor and delivery, or hospital intensive care departments. Mindfulness-based stress reduction interventions for the PN working in an intense psychiatric work environment can reduce the exhaustion linked to stress and burnout and provide an opportunity to utilize comfort not only for the distressed psychiatric patient but also for the psychiatric nurse. It is critical to meet the unmet needs of the psychiatric nurse through the framework of KCT. This DNP project consciously used KCT as it allowed mindfulness and comfort to reduce unmet needs of burnout and stress and opened the dialogue for more interventions to improve psychiatric care outcomes for the psychiatric patient. Future studies may utilize different project site locations with different demographic variables measured.

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Appendix A

Table of Evolution of Theory of Comfort

Table 1

Evolution of the Mid-Range Theory of Comfort for Outcomes Research

Context in which Comfort Occurs	Type of Comfort		
	<i>Relief</i>	<i>Ease</i>	<i>Transcendence</i>
Physical			
Psychospiritual			
Environmental			
Social			

Note. Adapted from *Evolution of the Mid-Range Theory of Comfort for Outcomes Research* by, K. Kolcaba, 2001.

Figure 1

The Conceptual Framework for a Theory of Comfort

Note. Adapted from *The Comfort* website by, K. Kolcaba & A. Bice-Braswell, 2007.
<https://www.thecomfortline.com>

Appendix B

Figure 2

Conceptual Framework for KCT Applied to Psychiatric Nurses

Note. Conceptual Framework for Comfort Theory applied to the Psychiatric Nurse.

Figure 3

Appendix C

CSUF IRB Approval

Date: 4-14-2024

IRB #: HSR-23-24-42

Title: Burnout and Stress Reduction in Psychiatric Nurses Through Mindfulness-Based Interventions

Creation Date: 8-17-2023

End Date:

Status: Approved

Principal Investigator: Erika Ubom

Review Board: Exempt Board

Sponsor:

Study History

Submission Type	Initial	Review Type	Exempt	Decision	Exempt
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Institutional Approval Letter

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301 Victoria Street Costa Mesa, CA 92627 * 949-574-3385

Institutional Approval Letter

05/23/23

This letter is to show that, I, Warren Bradley, as the CEO of College Hospital Costa Mesa, give permission to Erika Ubom, PMHNP-BC to conduct the project titled "Burnout and Stress Reduction in Psychiatric Nurses Through Mindfulness-based Stress Reduction Strategies" on the following unit(s) CHCM Inpatient units: North, South, East, West and CSU unit.

Upon obtaining all necessary clearances from the Nursing Research Council, and at College Hospital Costa Mesa, and after obtaining the necessary IRB determination/approval, the above-named project lead is allowed to:

- (1) collect demographic data that includes age, gender, education level, marital status, years of work experience, and employment status, as well as level of burnout according to the Maslach Burnout Inventory-Human Services Survey and level of stress according to the Perceived Stress Scale-10.
- (2) access necessary documents/data according to the above-mentioned data listed on item (1)
- (3) conduct necessary interactions with staff/patients relevant to the "Burnout and Stress Reduction in Psychiatric Nurses Through Mindfulness-based Stress Reduction Strategies" DNP project
- (4) distribute and recruit participants using flyers, staff emails, and attend staff meetings. Also, distribute QR codes via Qualtrics for electronic submission of pre- and -post survey data. All data collected will be anonymous.

The project lead is responsible for ensuring that all activities related to conducting the project are in compliance with the policies that govern practice, HIPPA, and research and research-related regulations at College Hospital Costa Mesa and its covered entities.

If you have any questions or concerns, please do not hesitate to contact me directly.

Signature:

Name: Warren Bradley

Title: Interim C.E.O.

Contact Information:

Signature:

Name:

Title:

Contact Information:

Appendix D

Consent for Participation

California State University, Fullerton, Research Study Consent Form

Study Title: Burnout & Stress Reduction in Psychiatric Nurses Through Mindfulness-Based Stress Reduction Interventions

Protocol Number: HSR-23-24-42

Researchers: Erika Ubom, DC, PMHNP-BC, Manal Alatrash, PhD, RN Laura Sarff, DNP, RN, MBA, CPHQ, NEA-BC

You are being asked to participate in a pretest-posttest, single-group interventional design study by Erika Ubom, DC, PMHNP-BC, Manal Alatrash, PhD, RN and Laura Sarff, DNP, RN, MBA, CPHQ, NEA-BC. This consent form explains the study and your participation if you decide to join. Please read the form in its entirety. Ask the researcher any questions you may have. A detailed explanation will be provided to you, so you fully understand the study. You have every right not to participate in this study; even if you decide halfway through the study you no longer wish to participate, you can drop out. It is your right to quit at any time. There will be no penalty, consequence, loss of services, or benefits rendered if you decide not to participate in the study.

What is this study about?

This pretest-posttest design study is conducted to decrease burnout and stress in the psychiatric nurse through mindfulness-based stress reduction interventions.

You are being asked to take part because you are 18 years or older, speak English, and provide direct nursing care to psychiatric patients in the CSU or IPU.

You cannot participate in this study if you are under 18 years old, do not provide direct nursing care to psychiatric patients, or do not speak English. Also, if you are experiencing an exacerbation of mental health symptoms, you cannot participate in this study.

Taking part in the study will take about 30-60 minutes. Participants will govern the amount of time they will spend on MBSR strategy performance. Suggested 15-minute minimum time frame.

What will I be asked to do if I am in this study?

If you participate in the study, you will be asked to read and sign the consent form.

You will be asked to provide baseline data, such as age, gender, marital status, education, employment status, and years of experience.

You will be asked to complete questionnaires on current burnout and stress levels. You will also be asked to complete surveys on whether you have practiced MBSR interventions daily at work and home. It will take about 20 to 30 minutes to complete the surveys and questionnaire. You may refuse to answer any questions in the surveys.

You will be asked to participate in the practice of MBSR interventions at least 3 times per day, and then you will be asked daily to report on whether you used the MBSR interventions and how often you used. Specifically, you will be taught neck, spine, upper and lower extremities stretching techniques, deep breathing techniques, and mindful meditation. In addition, you will be encouraged to ask questions.

After the MBSR education session, you will be contacted by the project investigator via text for a check-in weekly to see how MBSR interventions have helped you. In addition, if there are any barriers that you might be facing, the project investigator will determine the best intervention to remove that barrier.

At the end of the project, you will be asked to fill out a post-intervention survey about burnout and stress.

The surveys and data collected by the project investigator will be kept in a locked safe in a locked office. The project investigator will only have access to the office. In addition, the data will be on a password-protected computer only known to the project investigator. Once analysis of data and interpretation of the findings is complete, all data will be erased.

Are there any benefits to me if I am in this study?

The potential benefits to you for participating in this project are a decrease in burnout and stress while working in the CSU or IPU.

If you participate in this project, you may help others in their approach to decreasing burnout and stress while working in a psychiatric hospital.

Are there any risks to me if I am in this study?

The potential risks of participating in this study could be the psychological stress associated with the memory of challenging situations that may have occurred on the CSU or IPUs.

Will my information be kept anonymous or confidential?

The data for this study is being collected confidentially. Identifying information will not be linked to you, just collected. All information will be kept confidential and stored on a password-protected laptop in the project investigator's locked office. The Project investigator will place the signed consent form in an envelope that will be stored in a locked drawer in the locked project investigator's locked office.

Will there be any costs or payments for being in this study?

There will be no costs to you for taking part in this study.

Who can I talk to if I have questions?

If you have questions about this project or the information in this form, please contact the project investigator Erika Ubom at (██████████) or e-mail eubom001@csu.fullerton.edu

If you have questions about your rights as a quasi-experimental project participant or would like to report a concern or complaint about this project, please contact the Institutional Review Board at (██████████) or e-mail irb@fullerton.edu

What are my rights as a DNP project volunteer?

Your participation in this project is entirely voluntary. You may choose not to be a part of this project. You will not be penalized if you choose not to participate. You may choose not to answer specific questions or to stop participating at any time.

What does my signature on this consent form mean? Your signature on this form means that:

- You understand the information given to you in this form
- You have been able to ask the researcher questions and state any concerns
- The researcher has responded to your questions and concerns
- You believe you understand the research study and the potential benefits and risks involved.

Statement of Consent

I have carefully read and/or had the terms used in this consent form and their significance explained to me. By signing below, I agree that I am at least 18 and agree to participate in this project. You will be given a copy of this signed and dated consent form to keep.

Name of Participant (please print) _____

Signature of Participant _____

Date _____

Signature of Investigator X _____

Date _____

Appendix E

Recruitment Flyer

BURNOUT & STRESS REDUCTION THROUGH MINDFULNESS STRATEGIES QUALITY IMPROVEMENT PROJECT

SEEKING RESEARCH PARTICIPANTS

MORE ABOUT THIS STUDY

THIS IS A QI PROJECT THAT AIMS TO

- (A) IDENTIFY CAUSES OF BURNOUT AND STRESS IN PSYCH NURSES
- (B) ASSESS CHANGES IN BURNOUT AND STRESS LEVELS BEFORE AND AFTER THE IMPLEMENTATION OF MINDFULNESS STRATEGIES
- ATTEND AN EDUCATIONAL SESSION AND LEARN MINDFULNESS MUSCLE STRETCHING, DEEP BREATHING, AND MEDITATION STRATEGIES

WHO CAN PARTICIPATE

- YOU CAN PARTICIPATE IF YOU ARE 18 YEARS OR OLDER, SPEAK ENGLISH, AND PROVIDE DIRECT NURSING CARE AS AN NP, RN, LVN OR CNA TO PSYCH PATIENTS IN THE CRISIS STABILIZATION UNIT OR INPATIENT UNITS

BENEFITS

- INCREASE YOUR WELLBEING BY DECREASING YOUR SENSE OF BURNOUT AND STRESS WHILE WORKING WITH PSYCH PATIENTS

CONTACT THE RESEARCHER

Erika Ubom, CSUF Doctoral Candidate
 eubom001@csu.fullerton.edu, (██████████)

Appendix F

Mindfulness-Based Stress Reduction Education Instructions

Mindfulness is a gentle approach to exploring an individual's present time, day by day, hour by hour, minute by minute. The willingness to achieve peace through the removal of burnout and stress can be mastered through the following interventions:

Body relaxation via Mindful muscle stretching to be performed 3 times per day or when triggered.

Shoulder raises – while sitting, with arms relaxed, slowly lift shoulders toward the head, hold for 5 seconds, then lower shoulders down; do this 7 to 10 times.

Shoulder rolls – while sitting in a relaxed position, lift your shoulders towards your ears, back toward your spine, and down toward your toes; do this 7 to 10 times.

Trapezius stretch – while sitting, align posture/spine, use the right hand, and bring overhead, covering the left ear, lateral flex neck toward the right shoulder, apply tolerable pressure, and hold for 10 seconds; perform on the left side.

Hamstring stretch – flex at the trunk, place the plantar surface of hands on the floor, push fingers toward the floor, or extend leg outward and flex trunk toward extended leg; hold for 10 seconds, perform 3 to 5 times.

Mindfulness music therapy via YouTube mindfulness music playlist while at home or on work break

Subtle, low, relaxing music will be played before deep breathing and meditation intervention begins. The music will calm the mind and allow burnout and stress to leave the body and focus the mind. Music will be played continuously until the completion of MBSR education. Then, participants will be instructed to play calm, relaxing music at home while practicing MBSR interventions.

Mindful deep breathing to be performed 3 times per day or when triggered.

Sit in a relaxed posture and slowly inhale through the nose concentrating on the expansion of the lungs; hold for 3 seconds, and then exhale through the mouth; do this whenever the work environment triggers an individual.

Mindful meditation to be performed 3 times per day or when triggered.

Sit in a relaxed posture with feet flat and hands on your lap; close your eyes, engage in deep breathing, focus on inhalation and exhalation, become aware of external sensations and what is felt internally; block all negative thoughts, receive all positive thoughts instead; do this three times per shift/ per day or when time permits at work. Access to a quiet, uninterrupted environment will allow for more profound meditation.

Appendix G

MBI-HSS (Not full survey)

For use by Erika Ubom only. Received from Mind Garden, Inc. on April 20, 2023

Human Services Survey

Christina Maslach & Susan E. Jackson

The purpose of this survey is to discover how various people working in human services or the helping professions view their job and the people with whom they work closely.

Because people in a wide variety of occupations will answer this survey, it uses the term *recipients* to refer to the people for whom you provide your service, care, treatment, or instruction. When answering this survey please think of these people as recipients of the service you provide, even though you may use another term in your work.

Instructions: On the following page are 22 statements of job-related feelings. Please read each statement carefully and decide if you ever feel this way about *your* job. If you have *never* had this feeling, write the number "0" (zero) in the space before the statement. If you have had this feeling, indicate *how often* you feel it by writing the number (from 1 to 6) that best describes how frequently you feel that way. An example is shown below.

Example:

How often:	0	1	2	3	4	5	6
	Never	A few times a year or less	Once a month or less	A few times a month	Once a week	A few times a week	Every day

How often 0-6	Statement:
1. _____	I feel depressed at work.

If you never feel depressed at work, you would write the number "0" (zero) under the heading "How often." If you rarely feel depressed at work (a few times a year or less), you would write the number "1." If your feelings of depression are fairly frequent (a few times a week but not daily), you would write the number "5."

MBI - Human Services Survey - MBI-HSS: Copyright ©1981 Christina Maslach & Susan E. Jackson. All rights reserved in all media. Published by Mind Garden, Inc., www.mindgarden.com

MBI – Human Services Survey – MBI-HSS:

I feel emotionally drained from my work.

I have accomplished many worthwhile things in this job.

I don't really care what happens to some recipients.

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Permission Letter

www.mindgarden.com

To Whom It May Concern,

The above-named person has made a license purchase from Mind Garden, Inc. and has permission to administer the following copyrighted instrument up to that quantity purchased:

Maslach Burnout Inventory forms: Human Services Survey, Human Services Survey for Medical Personnel, Educators Survey, General Survey, or General Survey for Students.

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Sample Items:

MBI - Human Services Survey - MBI-HSS:

I feel emotionally drained from my work.
I have accomplished many worthwhile things in this job.
I don't really care what happens to some recipients.

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MBI - Human Services Survey for Medical Personnel - MBI-HSS (MP):

I feel emotionally drained from my work.
I have accomplished many worthwhile things in this job.
I don't really care what happens to some patients.

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MBI - Educators Survey - MBI-ES:

I feel emotionally drained from my work.
I have accomplished many worthwhile things in this job.
I don't really care what happens to some students.

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Cont'd on next page

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MBI - General Survey - MBI-GS:

I feel emotionally drained from my work.
In my opinion, I am good at my job.
I doubt the significance of my work.

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MBI - General Survey for Students - MBI-GS (S):

I feel emotionally drained by my studies.
In my opinion, I am a good student.
I doubt the significance of my studies.

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Sincerely,

A handwritten signature in black ink, appearing to read "Robert Most", with a long horizontal line extending to the right.

Robert Most
Mind Garden, Inc.
www.mindgarden.com

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**Permission for Erika Ubom to administer 100 copies
within three years of April 20, 2023**

Maslach Burnout Inventory™

MBI Forms and Scoring Keys:

Human Services - MBI-HSS
Medical Personnel - MBI-HSS (MP)
Educators - MBI-ES
General - MBI-GS
Students - MBI-GS (S)

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By Christina Maslach, Susan E. Jackson, Michael P. Leiter,
Wilmar B. Schaufeli & Richard L. Schwab

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PSS

INSTRUCTIONS:

The questions in this scale ask you about your feelings and thoughts during **THE LAST MONTH**. In each case, please indicate your response by placing an "X" over the circle representing **HOW OFTEN** you felt or thought a certain way.

	Never 0	Almost Never 1	Sometimes 2	Fairly Often 3	Very Often 4
1. In the last month, how often have you been upset because of something that happened unexpectedly?	<input type="radio"/>				
2. In the last month, how often have you felt that you were unable to control the important things in your life?	<input type="radio"/>				
3. In the last month, how often have you felt nervous and "stressed"?	<input type="radio"/>				
4. In the last month, how often have you felt confident about your ability to handle your personal problems?	<input type="radio"/>				
5. In the last month, how often have you felt that things were going your way?	<input type="radio"/>				
6. In the last month, how often have you found that you could not cope with all the things that you had to do?	<input type="radio"/>				
7. In the last month, how often have you been able to control irritations in your life?	<input type="radio"/>				
8. In the last month, how often have you felt that you were on top of things?	<input type="radio"/>				
9. In the last month, how often have you been angered because of things that were outside your control?	<input type="radio"/>				
10. In the last month, how often have you felt difficulties were piling up so high that you could not overcome them?	<input type="radio"/>				

SPECIAL TERMS No83659

These User License Agreement Special Terms (Special Terms) are issued between Mapi Research Trust ("MRT") and Erika Ubom (User).

These Special Terms are in addition to any and all previous Special Terms under the User License Agreement General Terms.

These Special Terms include the terms and conditions of the User License Agreement General Terms, which are hereby incorporated by this reference as though the same was set forth in its entirety and shall be effective as of the Special Terms Effective Date set forth herein.

All capitalized terms which are not defined herein shall have the same meanings as set forth in the User License Agreement General Terms.

These Special Terms, including all attachments and the User License Agreement General Terms contain the entire understanding of the Parties with respect to the subject matter herein and supersedes all previous agreements and undertakings with respect thereto. If the terms and conditions of these Special Terms or any attachment conflict with the terms and conditions of the User License Agreement General Terms, the terms and conditions of the User License Agreement General Terms will control, unless these Special Terms specifically acknowledge the conflict and expressly states that the conflicting term or provision found in these Special Terms control for these Special Terms only. These Special Terms may be modified only by written agreement signed by the Parties.

1. User information

User name	Erika Ubom
Category of User	Student
User address	800 N. State College Blvd, Fullerton, 92831, United States
User VAT number	
User email	eubom001@csu.fullerton.edu
User phone	██████████
Billing information	800 N. State College Blvd, Fullerton, 92831, United States

2. General information

Effective Date	Date of acceptance of these Special Terms by the User : 26 Apr 2023
Expiration Date (Term)	Upon completion of the Stated Purpose
Name of User's contact in charge of the request	Erika Ubom

3. Identification of the COA

Name of the COA	PSS-10 - Perceived Stress Scale - 10 items
Author	Cohen S, Williamson GM
Copyright Holder	RST Assessments, LLC (USA)
Copyright notice	© Copyright RST Assessments, LLC. All Rights Reserved (2022)
Bibliographic reference	<p>Cohen, S. (1986). Contrasting the hassle scale and the perceived stress scale. <i>American Psychologist</i>, 41, 716-719 (Full text article)</p> <p>Cohen S and Williamson GM (1988). Perceived stress in a probability sample of the United States. In S. Spacapan & S. Oskamp (Eds.), <i>The Social Psychology of Health</i>. Newbury Park, CA: Sage (Full text article)</p>
Module(s)/version(s) needed	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • PSS-10

Appendix H

Demographic Survey

Gender: what is your gender?

- Male
- Female
- Non-binary

Age: What is your age?

- 18-21 years old
- 22-28 years old
- 29-35 years old
- 36-42 years old
- 43-50 years old
- 51-60 years old
- 60 + years old

Education: What is the highest level of education you have completed?

- High school diploma or GED
- Some college, no degree
- Vocational/Tech training
- Associate degree
- Bachelor's degree
- Master's degree
- Doctorate degree

Marital Status: What is your marital status?

- Single
- Married or domestic partnership
- Widowed
- Divorced
- Separated

Work Experience: What is your nursing experience?

- < less than 1 year of experience
- two to three years of experience
- three to five years of experience

five years or more of experience

Employment Status: What is your employment status?

- Full time
- Part-time
- Per Diem

Appendix I

MBSR Simple Questionnaire

Date _____

1) Did you perform the MBSR strategies today?

Yes

No

2) Which strategies did you perform and how many times?

Muscle stretching _____

Music Therapy _____

Deep Breathing _____

Meditation _____

A daily text will be sent out to remind you to perform MBSR strategies and to fill out this questionnaire

Appendix J

Table 2

Evaluation and Measurement of Outcomes

Variable	Operational Definition	Method of Measurement	Analysis
Burnout Level	Pre- and post-surveys on levels of burnout	MBI-HSS	T-tests
Stress Level	Pre- and post-surveys on levels of stress	PSS-10	T-tests
Number of PNs who use MBSR strategies at work or home	Number of psychiatric nursing staff who perform MBSR strategies while working and at home.	Control Charts	Volume of psychiatric nursing staff performing MBSR strategies
Identify causes of Burnout and Stress		MBI-HSS & PSS-10	Descriptive statistics: averages, standard deviations, percentages, frequencies

Appendix K

Table 3

Participant Sociodemographic Characteristics

Variable	<i>n</i>	%
Gender		
Female	7	63.64
Male	3	27.27
Age		
29-35 years old	3	27.27
22-28 years old	2	18.18
36-42 years old	4	36.36
43-50 years old	1	9.09
Education		
Bachelor's Degree	7	63.64
Vocational/Tech Training	2	18.18
Associate Degree	1	9.09
Employment		
Full-time	10	90.91
Experience		
Five or more years of experience	5	45.45
Less than one year of experience	1	9.09
2-3 years of experience	3	27.27
3-5 years of experience	1	9.09
Marital Status		
Divorced	1	9.09
Married or Domestic Partnership	5	45.45
Single	4	36.36

Note. N = 10

Appendix L

Table 4

Two-Tailed Paired Samples t-Test for the Difference Between Pre-EE and Post-EE

Variables	Mean	Standard Deviation	<i>t</i>	<i>p</i>	<i>d</i>
Pre- Emotional Exhaustion	3.31	1.01	5.57	<.001	1.76
Post- Emotional Exhaustion	1.49	0.82			

Note. N = 10. Degrees of Freedom for the t-statistic = 9. d represents Cohen's d.

Figure 3

Average Emotional Exhaustion (EE) Domain Scores

Table 5

Two-Tailed Samples t-Test for the Difference Between Pre-DP and Post-DP

Variables	Mean	Standard Deviation	<i>t</i>	<i>p</i>	<i>d</i>
Pre-DP	1.60	1.10	1.95	.083	0.62
Post-DP	0.74	0.92			

Note. N = 10. Degrees of Freedom for the t-statistic = 9. *d* represents Cohen's *d*.

Figure 4

Average Depersonalization (DP) Pre and Post Domain Scores

Table 6

Two-Tailed Paired Samples t-Test for the Difference Between Pre-PA and Post-PA

Variables	Mean	Standard Deviation	<i>t</i>	<i>p</i>	<i>d</i>
Pre-PA	4.06	1.38	-2.16	.059	0.68
Post-PA	5.04	0.20			

Note. N = 10. Degrees of Freedom for the *t*-statistic = 9. *d* represents Cohen's *d*.

Figure 5

Personal Accomplishment (PA) Pre- and Post-Domain Scores

Table 7

Two-Tailed Paired Samples t-Test for the Difference Between Pre-PS and Post-PS

Variables	Mean	Standard Deviation	<i>t</i>	<i>p</i>	<i>d</i>
Pre-PS	2.16	0.20	1.10	.301	0.35
Post-PS	1.99	0.37			

Note. N = 10. Degrees of Freedom for the *t*-statistic = 9. *d* represents Cohen's *d*.

Figure 6

Perceived Stress Scale (PSS) Pre and Post Domain Scores

Table 8

Summary Statistics Table for Interval and Ratio Variables of MBSR Interventions

Variable	Mean	Standard Deviation	<i>n</i>	SE _{<i>M</i>}	Min	Max	Skewness	Kurtosis
Muscle Stretching	7.55	28.38	58	3.73	0.00	219.00	7.32	52.03
Music Therapy	7.07	26.55	58	3.49	0.00	205.00	7.33	52.15
Deep Breathing	12.00	44.96	58	5.90	1.00	348.00	7.38	52.67
Meditation	5.59	21.00	58	2.76	0.00	162.00	7.30	51.90

Appendix M

Figure 7

Cumulative Total of MBSR Interventions Used

Figure 8

Deep Breathing c Chart Pre & Post Data

Figure 9

Music Therapy c Chart Pre & Post Data

Figure 10

Muscle Stretch c Chart Pre & Post Data

Figure 11

Meditation c Chart Pre & Post Data

